

JOURNAL OF RELIGION, CULTURE, AND PEACE EDUCATION

ACADEMIC ARTICLE

A Socio-Psychological Conflict Analysis Framework for the Historical Conflict of First Century Palestine - Robert Ottenhof

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Self-Determination, Human Rights, Political Economy, and Peacebuilding: A Systematic Literature Review - Bryon Lippincott

Motivated Reasoning and the Decision-Making of Coup Resisters: Choosing to Leave or Stay in the Tanintharyi Region, Southern Myanmar - Myo Aung

The Role of the Catholic Church in Peacebuilding During the Three-Year Post-Coup Period in Myanmar - Saw Franklin Danile Aye

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Journal of Religion, Culture, and Peace Education (ReCaPE)

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Cover Design by Bryon Lippincott

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Academic Article

A Socio-Psychological Conflict Analysis Framework for the Historical Conflict of First Century Palestine

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Abstract

Scholarship concerning first-century Palestine, the world of Jesus of Nazareth, has not placed a high priority on conflict as a context from which to consider socio-political realities of that time and place. This study advocates to view intractable conflict and related socio-psychological dynamics as a socio-political context. It explores the extent to which a socio-psychological conflict analysis framework can contribute to the understanding of life in first-century Israel. The work of Daniel Bar-Tal is the foundation for the developed model that uses historical markers, characteristics of intractable conflicts and themes of social beliefs as the three levels by which to analyze the conflict. The study suggests that a socio-psychologic approach to conflict analysis, based on the intractable nature of conflict, can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of socio-political realities in first-century Israel and deserves a more prominent place in conflict analysis for present-day conflicts.

Keywords

Bar-Tal, conflict analysis, intractable conflict, socio-psychology, first-century Israel

Introduction

This paper considers the socio-psychological dynamics of intractable conflict for the analysis of an historical conflict. I will explore the usefulness of a socio-psychological framework, based on Daniel Bar-Tal's scholarship, in the analysis of first-century Palestine under Roman occupation, the time of Jesus. A first question that arises has to do with the suitability of modern peace theory for the context of ancient societies and conflicts under imperial domination. A second question I consider, is the usefulness of the framework used for present-day conflicts, and the adaptability to the context of a specific conflict, whether historical or contemporary. The main goal of this paper is to explore the pertinence of the use of a socio-psychological approach to conflict analysis for first-century Palestine. While specifics of the historical setting are used to scrutinize the usefulness of the framework, this paper does not in itself make a in depth analysis of Israel under Roman occupation. For this study I use "Palestine" as the territory that corresponds roughly with modern-day Israel and Palestine. During the first-century different nomenclature was used but scholarship generally identifies the region during this time as Palestine. Israel is used for the people as an ethnic-national identity.

Daniel Bar-Tal Theory of Intractable Conflicts

Daniel Bar-Tal developed his theory of intractable conflicts over a period that stretches well beyond 30 years of research. His theory focusses on the macro-societal scale, identifying characteristics of intractability that are specific for this level. Bar-Tal maintains that intractable conflicts have qualitative differences from conflicts for which we usually find peaceful resolutions. Intractable conflicts are not merely more intense and complex, they develop specific mechanisms that make them intractable. These mechanisms develop as the result of "pathological societal adaptations to difficult conflict situations" (Reykowski, 2015, p. 8).

Bar-Tal explains that under the influences of protracted conflicts, societies form a socio-psychological infrastructure of conflict. The three elements of this infrastructure are the collective memory, the ethos of conflict, and the collective emotional orientation. The collective memory forms the shared historical narrative and helps to develop the in-group's social identity. Under intractable conflict conditions the collective memory is dominated by conflict related themes. The distortion of the conflict realities and the justification of hostility toward the out-group, contribute to the crystallization of a self-righteous and ethnocentric narrative which becomes a barrier to peacebuilding (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 172). The ethos of conflict refers to the central shared societal beliefs by which the group understands the conflict

and by which it set its conflict goals. Where the collective memory provides a group narrative of the past, and how it arrived at the present, the ethos of conflict forms the foundation by which a cognitive view of the present and goals for the future are developed. The conflict ethos comprises eight societal core beliefs that are used in this study to form the third level of features for the conflict analysis model. The collective emotional orientation is the result of a society's common sensitivity to shared emotional experiences. Under intractable circumstances a society fosters commonly held emotional values and reactions. Typical reactions under prolonged conflict are negative collective emotions like fear, angst, hatred, anger, and humiliation; but also, positive emotions such as pride and hope. Emotions are a strong motivator for conflict behavior (Halperin, 2016, p. 21).

The socio-psychological infrastructure shapes the shared narratives of a society and affects the function of its institutes. The infrastructure becomes integrated into cultural symbols and can dominate many aspects of daily life. Intractability is the result of evolvement of a system of interconnected collective beliefs, attitudes, and emotional orientations. The infrastructure develops mechanisms that paradoxically are meant to move toward peace, yet create barriers for peacebuilding that cause the conflict to persist or to escalate.

Intractable Conflict as a Context

Any analysis of Israel under Roman occupation needs to consider the context. Many have made analyses that investigate historical, cultural, socio-political, and socio-religious contexts of that time. From the field of peace studies, I propose an analysis that considers intractable conflict as a context from which to examine life in first-century Israelite society. The intractable nature of conflict leads over time to significant changes in the psychological dynamics of a society. It is these adaptations in socio-psychology that become the main reasons behind the perpetuation and escalation of the conflict (Bar-Tal, 2023, p. 18).

A socio-psychological approach to conflict analysis is interested in the thoughts and feelings of individuals and societies about the conflict and its actors. Shared thoughts and feelings underpin the development of a society's narratives and the motivations of conflict behavior. While the development of a socio-psychological repertoire is the result of adapting and coping under difficult and prolonged conflict realities, the repertoire becomes a foundation for conflict supporting narrative and the emergence of a culture of conflict (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 247). A society's intent to create peaceful ways under intractable conflict realities, results in socio-

psychological adaptations that eventually become obstacles to peace and instigators of the conflict.

To gain a more comprehensive understanding of Israel's society during the first century, it seems important to consider the intractable nature of the conflict that doubtlessly impacted the lives of the people of Israel. The objective of this study is to develop of socio-psychological framework that is suitable for the analysis of first-century Israel under Roman occupation.

Since the notion of socio-psychology in peace studies is developed in modern conflict settings, application to conflict in ancient Palestine needs to be done with some degree of care. Like other scholars of intractable conflicts, Bar-Tal mainly purposes the use of his theory towards the resolution of conflicts, in terms of de-escalating and ultimately ending the conflict once deemed intractable (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 323; Halperin & Hameiri, 2015, p. 174). In the context of first-century Israel under Roman imperial occupation resolution would not have been perceived in the same way. Resolve for Israelite society might have been within the bounds of a best possible peaceful way of living under occupation; developing a culture of peace within a culture of conflict. To think of peace agreements or liberation from Rome, might have been unrealistic, or far-off goals at best. Socio-psychological processes of intractable conflicts develop barriers to peace that would need to be considered with both options of remedy of the conflict in mind.

I consider only general socio-psychological dynamics of Israelite society to confirm relevance of the framework for the specific conflict at hand. A logical second step, which goes beyond the space available in this study, is the application of this framework to the in-depth analysis of specific socio-psychological dynamics of Israel under Roman occupation. I propose a framework that makes use of three schemes: the conflict history, intractable conflict characteristics, and the main societal beliefs that underpin a society's conflict supportive narratives.

Historical Markers of a Shared Narrative

The historical background of a conflict includes a number of events that form a foundation for the current conflict. Each conflict party selects and interprets historic events in a way that gives meaning to and supports the in-group's narrative. From these historical markers a society creates narratives that give meaning to the conflict dynamics in a way that portrays the in-group favorable. Historical markers function to frame present conflict events. New conflict related

incidents are interpreted by means of a pattern through which historical events are perceived. Bar-Tal explains how current events in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict are shaped with the holocaust as a historical marker in the collective memory (Eldar & Bar-Tal, 2024). The analysis of a conflict begins with the historical markers of a societal narrative and how these function to shape the perceived historical reality.

This study considers the suitability of using Israel's historical markers in the analysis of the national narrative during the first century. The larger narrative is accepted by most members of society. Within a society various minor narratives develop dividing larger society into social groupings. Smaller narrative can be viewed as alternative interpretations or adaptations of the larger narrative. First-century Israel, occupied under the Roman empire, selected several key markers of its history to become pillars of its national narrative. The Exodus story, in which Israel was freed from Egyptian rule and slavery, established Israel as a chosen people under God. Israel's God made a covenant promising Israel an identity as a people and the geographical territory of Israel (Canaan) as their land. The story supports the notion of nationhood and land as sacred, uncompromisable values. In addition, it predisposes Israel to view itself as victims in an unequal conflict, yet as favorable in sight of God. The historical event underpins values vital for the people's self-perceived social identity.

Israel's independent rule under king David and his son Solomon, during the tenth century BC, became the lamented ideal past and hoped-for vision for the future. During the second temple period, the idealization of David and Solomon, were not only a glorification of the past, but also reveal an anticipation of a possible future kingdom (Schweitzer, 2010, p. 469). Prosperity, peace, national identity, and possession of the land under a God-appointed king (Messiah) had become key markers of Israel's past and for many uncompromisable goals for her future. Many texts circulating during the first century express the expectations of a restoration of Israel's time of grandeur (Nickelsburg, 2005, p. 9).

The past occupations under consecutively Assyria, Babylonia, Persia, and Greece added to the dominant theme of foreign occupation in Israel's national narrative. Oppression and suffering under foreign domination strengthened Israel's self-identification with victimhood. Even though Israel's prophets pointed to Israel's unfaithfulness to God as the reason for foreign occupation, Israel's narrative firmly embraced the concept that justice would be established through God's punishment of Israel's enemies. Both these ideas did not necessarily remove Israel's self-understanding as long-term victims under foreign oppression. First-century Israel,

in a way, was still awaiting the end of exile (Wright, 1992, p. 299), the overthrow of foreign rule, and the restoration of God's covenant objectives for Israel.

In recent history, Israel had experienced a century of independence under the Hasmonean kingdom. In their fight for independence from Greek (Seleucid) occupation, renewed national ambitions arose which were still present during the first century. The Israelites celebrated the victory over the Greek occupiers and the rededication of the temple in Jerusalem with the annual feast of Hannukah (John 10:22). This victory over a dominant foreign power must still have been fresh in the collective memory of the people in the time of Jesus. It is likely that these memories strengthened patriotic sentiments, collective self-identity, and a feeling of superiority over others as a nation chosen by God. If armed resistance against the Seleucid empire had brought victory, then hope, even if latent, for a liberated Israel could well have been part of a first-century Jewish expectation.

More recent events and regional conflicts could have been added to support the dominant narrative. The invasion of Rome, their military often brutal force, and the occupation, either directly (Roman governors) or through (Herodian) client kings, crushed Israelite hopes and goals for an independent glorious kingdom. Josephus tells about numerous battles against Rome, and of local uprisings against the illegitimate occupier (McLaren, 1998, pp. 150–158). The Jewish Wars of AD 66 through 135 disclose sentiments that fueled the Israelite resistance that was already present before the beginning of the revolt that escalated in 66 AD.

Characteristic of Intractability

This section is organized around the question of how features of intractability impact the lives of a society involved in the conflict. A socio-psychological approach seeks to understand the way people perceive the conflict dynamics: how do members of a conflict party think and feel in the midst of protracted conflict realities? The characteristics are taken from Bar-Tal (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 37). I have added considerations for additional features based on specifics of the conflict under investigation.

1) *Totality of Goals:*

Totality refers to the nature and scope of the conflict goals. Goals are significant only when pursued in their entirety. Compromise devaluates the goal below its desired outcome. Each conflict party perceives their goals as completely incompatible with the goals of the rival. The goals are essential, related to basic needs and values of the in-group and considered

indispensable for the group's identity and existence. It is perceived that it is impossible to satisfy the goals of both parties in harmony, because the out-group's objectives demand compromise of the in-group goals.

In first-century Israel the goals would have included worldview fundamentals such as the land and Israel's socio-religious identity markers that defined them as a people (Wright, 1992, pp. 224–232). This included cultural practices, the law and the temple cult. The land was perceived as sacred, given to Israel by God. Giving up the land to foreign occupiers was equal to unfaithfulness to God's covenant. Self-determination, with a utopian view of a renewed kingdom under God's appointed king (messiah) was a goal imbedded in Israel's sacred scriptures. In addition, the desire for cultural and religious freedom, with the Torah as Israel's law, freedom for identity-marking cultural practices (sabbath, food-laws, circumcision), and the renewal of the temple, were all goals that stood in direct opposition to Roman rule and Hellenizing cultural trends. These goals were vital elements of Israel's perceived social identity and worldview, seen as total and not open to compromise.

Most likely the majority of Israelites perceived their national goals as incompatible with the aims of their Roman occupier and their client kings. Roman occupation was a threat to the existence of Israel as a nation. Realities of daily life for the non-elite would have contributed to this perception. Lack of material wealth, military and economic oppression made daily life challenging for most common Israelites. The loss of ownership of land would have gravely impacted an agricultural society (Pastor, 1997, pp. 98–102, 150–151). For many, societal goals might have been little more than a distant utopian dream, with little concrete application. Under prolonged occupation and at times of relative socio-political stability, people would have adapted to life under Rome and gone about daily life in a normative way (Bar-Tal & Schnell, 2013, p. 11). Yet at times of increased conflict and among emerging sectarian movements, sentiments of greater ambitions, point to the latent existence of national goals (Newman, 2006, p. 238). The existence of utopian goals (for conflict resolution) and goals for normative life under occupation were not held exclusively.

2) *Violence*

Violence changes the conflict qualitatively. Violence is the most critical ingredient that causes a manageable conflict to turn into an intractable one.

It seems that almost every conflict over essential goals leads to violence, as no side is willing to compromise in the initial stages of the conflict. Violence unfortunately is a human signal of power and determination that is used in order to demonstrate the seriousness of a group's contentions (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 42).

It is generally agreed upon that the Roman occupation and Herodian rule were brutally violent and military controlled (Freyne, 1998, p. 57; Grabbe, 2021, p. 7). During the turn of the millennium armed resistance groups opposed Roman occupation, causing unproportionate violent responses from the Roman military. It debated to what extent military and armed group violence were part of the "normal" experience of common Israelites of that time. Bar-Tal reminds us that it is not necessary to undergo direct violence oneself, but that identification with the in-group's suffering is sufficient to experience the psychological consequences of trauma (Bar-Tal, 2023, p. 21).

It is argued that violent conflict events were not continuous, and that Herodian rule knew times of relative peace (Goodman, 2007, p. 22.2). Nonetheless, it seems unlikely that the non-elite Israelite population would live without awareness of military subjugation, whether through direct experience or co-experience of other in-group members. Violence under this heading point mostly to direct violence, but structural and cultural violence play an equal important role in intractable conflicts (Galtung, 1990, p. 291).

3) *Zero-Sum in Nature*

The conflict parties perceive that any compromise in goals or any giving towards the rival means a loss to the in-group. Any gain for the out-group is equal to loss for the in-group, and thus compromise is seen as a threat to in-group existence. Nothing less than the whole of the in-group's goals is necessary for survival and victory in the conflict. It is important to get a clear view of the goals of the conflict parties. As in the case of first-century Israel, not all goals are necessarily explicit. While goals related to the land and ethnic identity might be more overt, goals related to religious-cultural aims might seem to be less zero-sum in nature, but could be the driving force behind a perceived existential threat.

To many in Israel of that time the land as a whole, could not be compromised, as it was an essential element of Israel's identity and covenant relation with God. The land was both perceived as a total goal, because it held sacred meaning only in its totality. It was perceived as zero-sum, because any territory taken by the rival meant direct loss to Israel and a threat to

national identity. Israel had for centuries negotiated daily life between assimilation and resistance of Hellenizing cultural influences. Society at large was polarized between those that allowed a greater degree of Greco-Roman culture into daily life, and those that adhered stricter to Judean (Jewish) culture and practices. Internal conflicts as well as resistance movements to Rome and Herodian rule were fueled by cultural sentiments. Some did not view socio-cultural assimilation as a threat to Israel's identity, and some might have even seen it as a way to preserve distinct identity under foreign influence. Other might have perceived the Greco-Roman cultural aspects in a more zero-sum context.

4) Centrality

The prolonged nature of the conflict has caused it to take a central position in individual and collective life. Thoughts and feelings related to the conflict are easily accessible and become foundational for the way in which people make decisions for daily life. The conflict and its consequences become evident in many aspects of daily life, both in individual as collective aspects.

“The centrality feature has a sociopsychological element because it indicates an intensive preoccupation with the conflict by society members on both cognitive and emotional levels” (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 46).

The constant presence of conflict realities, causes people to normalize conflict realities, losing sight of the fact that there are other ways to engage in life. The prominent place the conflict takes in people's life results in normalization and routinization of the conflict. This socio-psychological process becomes an obstacle to peace because there is no perceived urgency to end the conflict.

The main difficulty in determining people's thought and feelings in a historical conflict is the fact that socio-psychological dynamics are usually only implied within the historical texts. General conjecture can be made from the sources when these describe a degree of commonness in the incidence of violence. Brutal episodes of military domination, harsh economic oppression, and perceived existential threat (evident in for example Josephus' writings) would lead to a central nature of the conflict. I suggest that Jewish writing of that period and even material remains can call attention to the extent of a central character of the conflict. I explore these in greater detail in the second paper, expanding upon this study.

5) *Unsolvable Nature*

The society engaged in conflict perceives that the conflict is unsolvable in peaceful ways. In addition, the in-group might believe it is unlikely the war will end, even by military means. This produces a sense of hopelessness within society that lacks a positive envisioning of the future. The only perceived way to a positive future, out of the conflict stalemate, is total annihilation of the rival group. Perceived insolvability develops after prologued conflict which has seen numerous attempts to make peace either through armed campaigns or diplomatic means. Insolvability is a pure socio-psychological dynamic, because the conflict is perceived as unsolvable (Bar-Tal, 2013, p. 48). Again, the socio-psychological dynamic becomes the force that perpetuates the conflict.

For the purpose of first-century Israel, as with the previous point, purely psychological dynamics, perceptions about the conflict, are surmised from implicit accounts within the ancient sources. First, some of the conditions that lead to a societal belief that the conflict people are part of is insolvable are clearly present at that time. With the independence under Hasmonean rule in the recent background, numerous attempts to overthrow Roman occupation had failed (Josephus). Normalization of life under Rome and cultural adaptations to Greek cultural domination are results of prolonged conflict and the loss of a belief in a timely resolution.

6) *Extensive Investments*

Maintaining an intractable conflict demands extensive material and psychological investment. Material investments include the development of a societal military infrastructure that supports involvement in a prolonged conflict. This includes not only acquiring weapons and organizing the military, but also the mobilization of in-group members. The psychological investments relate to development of the societal ethos of conflict that justifies the in-group's position and role in the conflict and mobilizes society with a positive self-image. Members of society develop adaptive thoughts and emotional orientations in order to cope with the challenges of the conflict. The psychological investments have a tremendous impact on people's daily lives. Society sacrifices opportunities for developments and improvements in ordinary life to continue the conflict. Normalization of the conflict supports the emergence of a culture of conflict in which conflict investments are inevitable.

Israelites of the first-century did not support a national military and investments into local resistance groups or defensive weapons must have been minimal. More was invested in terms

of mobilizing the people for a “Israelite way of living” in the context of Roman rule and Hellenization. Ways that supported national sentiments were easily interpreted as opposition to Rome and military responses could be brutal. The possibility of loss of life or property was real for those involved in sectarian movements that threatened Rome’s ambitions. Yet a distinctive ethos of conflict developed that suggests Israel made significant psychological investments that reshaped societal ways of thinking and emotional orientation under the challenges of the conflict (Stone, 1985, p. 218).

7) *Protracted*

The last characteristic of intractable conflicts is its long life. These conflicts last at least a generation or twenty-five years. The protracted nature causes the conflict to be perceived as insolvable and it triggers the development of specific socio-psychological processes. The development of a socio-psychological infrastructure is distinctive to intractable conflicts.

It is evident that the conflict in Palestine at the time of Jesus was protracted even if just analyzed from the time of Roman occupation (63 BC).

Adaptations for the use in historical context

The socio-psychological conflict framework is developed in the context of modern wars and conflicts. Analysis of a conflict in an ancient society requires considerations about the make-up of societies of those days, and how these might affect the way in which features of intractability might have presented itself. One difference in societies of antiquity, such as first-century Israel, is the difference in social stratification. Israel was a (advanced) agrarian society under imperial rule (Kautsky, 1982), in which a large peasant class was ruled by a small aristocratic elite. Interaction between the classes was not as common as in modern societies. Another variance from present day conflicts is the context of living under empire, which brings different challenges to daily life and the variables of the ethos of conflict (Bar-Tal & Schnell, 2013, pp. 8–9). These differences with our modern context will need to be considered in my follow up paper dealing with the specific conflict dynamics of first-century Palestine.

Themes of Societal Beliefs

The collective memory and the ethos of conflict, together with the shared emotional orientation form the foundation of a society’s worldview. It is through this socio-psychological repertoire that people view and interpret events and reality, and make decisions. Bar-Tal proposes a set of beliefs that are the pillars of the socio-psychological repertoire of a society engaged in an

intractable conflict. These themes of shared beliefs underpin the conflict supporting narratives of the collective memory and the ethos of conflict.

1) Beliefs that justify societal goals

Collective beliefs about justification of the in-group's conflict goals are key in the development of the ethos of conflict and in the "freezing" of societal conflict supporting narratives. Justification of goals is built upon beliefs that are rooted in national ideology, shared national history, theology or religious adherence, culture, and nationalism. In addition, the instinct for self-preservation as a people (ethnic, national) adds to the weight of justification.

In the case of first-century Israel, societal goals were related to a geographical territory, self-determination, cultural and religious freedom, and nationalistic ideology, where all embedded in Israel's historical narrative. Israel viewed herself as a nation favored and chosen by God, who had given Israel the land previously known as Canaan. The land had been given to Israel after the time of Moses roughly fourteen centuries ago, and yet Israel had lived in the land under occupation for most of that time. As an ethnic people, divine chosen-ness, added to an ethnocentric preminent self-identification. In contrast to most other nations, who allowed for a wide variety of divine beings within their religious beliefs, Israel's religion proclaimed their God as the true God and all others false. The sacred value of the temple and its place in the life of Israel was central in Israel's worldview. The threat Roman occupation brought to these key elements of Israel's identity and ideology, and that perceived this threat as existential, bolstered the justification of Israel's conflict goals.

Roman imperial rule allowed for a certain degree of local autonomy under client-kingdom rule. While this could to a degree satisfy Israel's goals in terms of a more peaceful life under occupation, it could never be perceived as compatible with Israel's deep-seated desire for liberation or independence. Rome's version of peace for its subject nations (*pax Romana*) reduced Israel to servitude under taxation. Israel ultimately envisioned peace in the context of independent self-determination in covenant with Israel's God and under his appointed king. Peace would include the land God had promised to Israel by God, governed under a purified and uncorrupted temple system. For some this ideal might have not been more than a distant aspiration in which the realities of prolonged occupation had quenched any tangible dreams, and daily life took place under normalized occupation realities. Others found ways to envision these goals in concrete ways, as can be seen in the emerging narrative of first-century sectarian groups and literary streams preserved in texts of that time. It is a challenge to determine the

extent and the shape of goal-oriented narratives among the non-elite common people of Israel since most written and material sources belong to elite culture.

Occupation under a dominant empire, in which the military power imbalance is sizable, could easily enforce notions of victimhood and dehumanization of the occupier. Socio-economic oppression would further strengthen the negative image of the rival and the injustice of their goals, supporting a narrative that justifies one's own goals.

2) *Beliefs about societal security and personal safety*

Under intractable conflicts security of societal interests and the safety of its members can take on an overemphasized position in the national narrative. It often claims that the in-group's situation is unique and that the dangers can only be understood by members of the in-group. Security can become the highest priority in socio-political discourse. Furthermore, security is prioritized due to the perception that the conflict is a direct threat to the existence of the in-group.

The Israelites under Roman occupation believed their situation to be unique even though many neighboring nations suffered under the same imperial rule. The fact that Israel's national interests held sacred value, inseparable from their collective identity as God's people, underwrote the uniqueness of her position. The threat to Israel's sacred held interests were understood as an existential threat. This perceived uniqueness increased the need to protect and prioritize security. The dangers did not only come from Rome's military power, but came through Herodian forces and the Jerusalem aristocracy, cultural influences (Hellenization) and even conflicting factions within Israelite society. As an occupied society, the common people negotiated security between assimilation and resistance.

In Israel's worldview religious zeal was seen by some as directly connected to the active involvement national security concerns. To those that adhered to such a view (Maccabees, school of Shammai, Zealots, Sicarii) violence was a legitimate means and a sign of religious zeal, that opposed any threats to national security (Atkinson, 2016, p. 26). This connection between a concern for security and religious devoutness is not uncommon in intractable conflict contexts (Bar-Tal, 2023, p. 34).

Many in Israel would have acknowledged recurring violent episodes with the occupier as part of 'normal' life. For the non-elite masses, the negotiation between societal security, a fight for national recognition, and personal safety would have been normative. Under prolonged

occupation, socio-psychological adaptations would include coping strategies for a more ‘peaceful’ life under the challenges of occupation. Security concern for the common people needs to be viewed in this context.

3) *Beliefs about delegitimization of the rival*

Adverse societal beliefs about the rival group commonly develop under intractable conflicts. These beliefs develop as a negative oversimplification in an attempt to make sense in conflicting relationships with others. Delegitimization of others strengthens the in-group positive self-image, dehumanizes the out-group, and lowers the threshold to harm them.

Harm done to members of the in-group can be connected to violent episodes in the society’s history in which members suffered at the hands of other rivals. In the case of Israel, violence suffered under Herodian rule could have been associated with episodes of violence suffered under Egypt centuries earlier. The negative stereotype of Egypt in Israel’s historical narrative could cause delegitimization of Herodian elites.

Ethnocentrism functions to shape and bolster a positive self-identity (see below), and lower the view of other groups. Ethnocentrism is a characteristic of most collectivist dyadic cultures. In-group norms become universally valid and the out-group is viewed with hostility and treated as an inferior being (Malina, 1996, pp. 80, 81). Israel’s sacred scriptures identified Israel as God’s chosen people, valued above the other nations (Deut. 7:6). Furthermore, they were appointed as a “light to the nations” (Isa. 49:6).

4) *Beliefs about a collective positive self-image*

The development of a collective positive self-image is based on the in-group’s perception of its ethos and positive moral character. Events in its historical narrative are favorably interpreted to support the in-groups view of oneself. A new, polarized, reality is constructed supported by strongly bias myths and narratives in which the in-group becomes the moral hero and the out-group the villain (Bar-Tal, 2023, p. 37; Coleman, 2021, pp. 44–58). The out-group is portrayed as the sole instigator of violence, forcing the in-group, who desires peace over war, to respond with violence. The in-group is viewed as a peace-loving people, the out-group as the aggressor.

The narrative selects historical events in which its heroes are honored for their moral character in their victories over the enemy. Israel’s narrative commemorates heroes who have overcome their enemies with the favor of God, who have shown extraordinary bravery, men and women of great faith, whose religious fervor paralleled success in violent conflicts. These heroes

become models of Israel's positive self-image. During the first-century Israel would have honored the heroes in the stories that form the key historical markers. Moses in the exodus and liberation from Egypt, David in his military victories over his enemies (Philistines), through which God established Israel as a kingdom, and in more recent times the Maccabees in the defeat of their Greek rulers and rededication of the temple in Jerusalem.

5) *Beliefs about in-group victimization*

Beliefs about the in-groups just interests and a positive self-image serve as the foundation by which the in-group views itself as the sole victim in the conflict. Historical narratives set the stage for the in-group to self-identify with victimhood. New conflict event and emerging narratives supported by the whole of the societal belief system coerce the society to position oneself as victims and the out-group as aggressors.

First-century Israel used its historical markers to shape a narrative in which Israel became the sole victim. Enslavement in Egypt, invasion and deportation into exile under Assyria and Babylonia, and occupation by Greek and roman empires all strengthened Israel's self-understanding as victims in unequal power conflicts. New events are interpreted in terms of a role of victimhood which was taken on within the narrative of conflicts that took place decades or even centuries earlier.

The collective self-perception of victimhood is developed over a long time. Centuries of suffering at the hands of foreign powers creates a shared feelings of always being the victims in wars against powerful enemies. These national narrative markers become an imprint of the society's psyche, shaping the group's self-perceived social identity. While this cultural victimhood identity can be dormant at times of relative peace, it can be re-activated during conflict escalation.

6) *Beliefs about patriotism*

Bar-Tal connects a societal belief about patriotism, which notably arises in times of intractable conflicts, with the need to mobilize society members. Broad public support for the conflict is needed to maintain long-lasting wars. Societal support extends to a willingness to make ultimate sacrifices, loss of live, even loss of life of one's children, for the cause of the conflict. Participating in the conflict goals of society's main narrative is considered honorable and even a moral duty as a member of society. Those that lose their lives in the conflict are honored as heroes. Ancient societies like those in first-century Roman Palestine, and especially among the

elite, participation in war was viewed as noble service and duty to one's nation, and the most direct way to gain honor and glory (Armstrong, 2014, p. 15; Kautsky, 1982, p. 52).

Uncontested loyalty to the societal ideology is equated with loyalty to the nation and patriotism. Skepticism or diversions from the nationalistic narrative is judged as unpatriotic or even a risk to national security. Narratives that question the main societal goals or means, weaken the main narrative needed for the mobilization of society. Patriotism, as viewed by the dominant narrative, justifies, even glorifies, the sacrifices needed to be engaged in the conflict.

In first-century Israel, patriotism was related as support to Israel's nationalism. As a occupied nation, the national narrative was constantly under pressure from Greco-Roman imperial ideology. Support of identity markers and opposition to perceived foreign threats shaped the ways in which patriotic sentiments developed. The variations in Jewish thought and sectarian movements that formed during that time each redefined loyalty to Israel as a people in their own terms. The Maccabees, and later the Zealot movement, were especially known for their warlike narrative which equated zeal for Israel and God with a willingness to take up arms even at the cost of life (Farmer, 1982, p. 124). This variety of patriotism gained societal support during the first century AD, mobilizing Israelites to participate in the Jewish rebellion against Rome in 66.

7) *Beliefs about unity of the in-group*

The intractable nature of conflict heightens a society's commitment to achieve unity. During times of conflict a natural desire for unity among people is strengthened by the perception that unity is needed to resist an enemy. Unity becomes important for national security. Diversity, alternative narratives, and internal factions can be portrayed as a threat to the dominant narrative and national security. Even when a society is divided over internal issues, unity in terms of the conflict is highly valued. Beliefs about patriotism and unity mutually support each other.

It is difficult to know the beliefs about unity in first-century Israel. While Israel was unified under the kingship of David and Solomon, the people divided in the subsequent kingdom. Further disintegration as one nation took place during the period of exile and Israel's unity (and national identity) from there on was always difficult to define. Rome might have been an enemy that united Israel at times of conflict escalation. Further study is needed to apply this theme of societal belief to Israel of that time.

8) Beliefs about peace

Peace plays an important role in the narratives of societies engaged in intractable conflicts. Beliefs about a positive self-image (see above) include the idea that the in-group is the peaceable party in the conflict, the rival is perceived as the aggressor. The in-group is portrayed as a peace-loving society, driven by the enemy to respond with violence. The actions of the in-group are believed to be motivated by a pursuit for peace, the goal of any violent and military action is peace. Beside the function of bolstering a positive and moral self-image, the peace narrative gives hope to a society entangled in a long lasting and violent war (Bar-Tal, 2023, p. 45).

Ideas about war and peace are clearly evident in the Jewish literature of Jesus time. Beliefs about peace in Israel during the early Roman occupation were varied, and included beliefs in a just war approach to accomplish peace, but also more non-violent approaches (Flusser, 2007, p. 8; Trocmé, 2011, p. 88). The personal experience of those living during the first century did not include a first-hand knowledge of a peaceful society that is not engaged in conflict. It is not difficult to imagine that for most Israelites Rome was the obvious aggressor in the conflict. Likewise, a positive self-image as a victim of violence and as a peace-loving nation would have naturally formed in Israel's collective belief.

Conclusions

First, I conclude, at this stage of my research, that a socio-psychological framework, such as the one proposed here, can be useful for analysis of historical conflicts, such as the one in Roman Palestine. A more thorough application of the framework to the first-century Palestine conflict will have to show to what extent this preliminary conclusion is warranted. I realize that the model needs to be applied with some care to historical conflicts, because it was developed in the context of modern-day conflicts. Some adaptations might be required. The substantial different nature of ancient societies and the dynamics of occupation under empire will affect the socio-psychology of societies engaged in intractable conflicts.

Second, I propose that the model proposed in this study, making use of a three-layered analysis based on historical markers, characteristics of intractability, and themes of societal beliefs, it a pragmatic and meaningful way to apply a socio-psychological approach to conflict analysis. The model provides a comprehensive, though not exhaustive, representation of the socio-psychological framework developed by Daniel Bar-Tal. I anticipate that application of the framework to present-day intractable conflicts requires less conflict specific adaptations.

A logical step to follow this research is an in-depth application of this model to Israel's society in first-century Palestine. I hope to do this in a forthcoming paper. It is worthwhile considering the socio-psychological dynamics and processes that result from intractable conflicts and how these reflect on the one hand, ideas related to conflict resolution, the establishing of socio-political peace, and on the other, the pursuit of peaceful ways within a society at conflict.

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Research Articles

Self-Determination, Human Rights, Political Economy, and Peacebuilding: A Systematic Literature Review

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Bryon Lippincott is a Ph.D. student in the Peace Studies program at Payap University. His research explores the affective and rhetorical construction of social imaginaries in emerging technology discourse, with a specific focus on artificial intelligence. His dissertation develops a replicable analytic framework for tracing how affective-symbolic elements in multimodal public discourse shape competing visions of desirable futures and contribute to early-stage conflict dynamics. By examining how imaginaries of AI futures are formed and circulate across networked media, his work contributes to the development of peace imaginaries and offers insights into the role of affect, rhetoric, and political economy in shaping inclusion or polarization in complex sociotechnical environments

Authorship Declaration: The following article is an original work created solely by the submitting author, Bryon Lippincott

Abstract

Self-determination conflicts are an omnipresent reality in global geopolitics, resulting in significant loss of life, displacement of populations, and destruction of civil infrastructure. The prevalence of self-determination conflicts demands increased research into their causes and potential solutions to end the violence associated with them. The current peacebuilding literature lacks sufficient documentation of the theoretical and practical connections among self-determination, human rights, political economy. This systematic literature review documents, summarizes, and critiques the existing literature that makes direct connections between self-determination, human rights, and political economy, and, where possible, peacebuilding. A critical analysis of the identified articles reveals three emergent themes: profound disparities in priorities across stakeholders, extensive reliance on domination for extraction, and a lack of clarity regarding viable solutions.

Keywords: Human Rights, Political Economy, Peacebuilding, Self-determination, Systematic Literature Review

Introduction

Myanmar, Indonesia, Ethiopia, Palestine, and India are all home to ongoing self-determination conflicts. However, these represent only a few of the numerous ongoing self-determination conflicts worldwide that vary widely in size and intensity. The origins and causes of these conflicts are diverse, from historical grievances over marginalization and oppression to cultural disrespect to governance models that intentionally exclude minority groups from the decision-making process. Self-determination does not exist in a theoretical vacuum; it is shaped by practical and theoretical frameworks that clarify the dynamics of these conflicts.

The right to self-determination as enshrined in Article 55 of the UN Charter (United Nations, 1945) and many other UN Declarations and Covenants, particularly the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (United Nations, 1966a) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, (United Nations, 1966b) is an ongoing source of tension and conflict worldwide. While the right to self-determination is a core pillar of the universal human rights platform, the articles that establish it as a global foundation lack precision and clarity regarding its applicability and scope. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights define the right to self-determination as follows. “All peoples have the right of self-determination. By virtue of that right, they freely determine their political status and freely pursue their economic, social, and cultural development (United Nations, 1966a, 1966b, Article 1).” This foundational statement defines the broad scope of self-determination, encompassing political, economic, social, and cultural elements. These four foundations of self-determination are also critical aspects of the international human rights regime. They are also vital sub-sectors of study and analysis within the theoretical framework of political economy. This connective tissue, linking self-determination, human rights, and political economy, has received little attention in the scholarly literature on peacebuilding.

To clarify the scope of this review, it is necessary to define the three supporting concepts that structure the analysis: human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding. Human rights are commonly understood as rights inherent to all persons, although their meaning, origins, and implementation remain contested across different intellectual and political traditions (Dembour, 2010; Lippincott, 2024; Ty, 2023b; United Nations, 2025). In international human rights law, however, self-determination complicates this framework because the ICCPR and

ICESCR articulate it as a right of “peoples,” not merely of individuals. This creates an enduring tension between individual-centered human rights frameworks and collective claims to political status, cultural continuity, territorial control, and economic development (Bauböck, 2005).

Political economy provides a framework for analyzing how power and material interests shape governance, law, development, and access to resources (Ty, 2023a). Self-determination conflicts are often framed as legal, constitutional, or security problems, but they are also deeply embedded in political economy (Ty, 2023a, p. 68). They frequently involve struggles over land, mineral wealth, taxation, labor, trade routes, and the authority to determine how resources are governed and distributed (Fernando, 2017; Oldham et al., 2024; Rahman et al., 2024). A political economy lens therefore helps explain why self-determination claims often provoke resistance from states and international actors: such claims may threaten not only territorial integrity but also entrenched systems of extraction, accumulation, and geopolitical influence.

Peacebuilding, meanwhile, is concerned with the prevention, mitigation, and transformation of violent conflict (Gawerc, 2006; Schirch, 2022). Rather than treating peace as the mere absence of violence, many peacebuilding frameworks emphasize the importance of addressing structural inequalities, exclusion, and unresolved grievances (Galtung & Fischer, 2013; Randazzo, 2017; Schirch, 2022). This perspective is particularly relevant to self-determination conflicts, which often persist because underlying demands for dignity, recognition, political voice, and control over collective futures remain unaddressed. Schirch's (2022) work on decolonizing peacebuilding highlights the existing tensions between social justice approaches to peacebuilding and state-centric security and stability approaches to peacebuilding. Bringing peacebuilding into conversation with human rights and political economy allows this review to assess not only how self-determination is theorized, but also how the literature imagines pathways beyond domination, extraction, and recurring conflict.

This conceptual framing helps position the contribution of the present study. Rather than treating self-determination as an isolated legal principle, the review examines how existing scholarship connects it to broader debates over human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding, and what those connections reveal about the limitations of current responses to self-determination conflicts.

Considerable literature connects pairs of elements, such as self-determination and human rights or human rights and political economy. Still, few studies triangulate these three elements, and even fewer connect self-determination, human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding. Due to the limited scholarly works establishing connections between these critical frameworks, this paper engages in a critical systemic literature review of the academic literature connecting these four elements.

This article addresses the following research question:

1. What literature directly connects human rights, political economy, self-determination, and peacebuilding?
2. How does the literature frame the relationship among self-determination, human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding?

Methodology

This literature review utilizes a qualitative systematic mapping review methodology, as described by Grant and Booth (2009). This review maps, summarizes, and critically assesses the existing research on self-determination, human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding. It also identifies knowledge and evidence gaps that inform future research. The review framework includes five stages: “planning, which involves searching for evidence; screening evidence; in-depth review; critical appraisal; and describing the findings,” as adapted from James et al.’s (2016, p. 5) methodology.

Grounded in Berger and Luckman’s (1967) view that social reality is produced through shared meanings and institutionalized practice, I adopt a critical constructivist perspective that treats knowledge as historically situated and power-laden. Following Fanon (1963) and Said (1979), I continue with an awareness of how domination and exclusion shape the production of legitimacy and recognizability, and following Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) work on institutions, I treat durable structures of power as central to the interpretations of reality that stabilize and become consequential.

Planning begins with selecting key terms that define the search parameters. This review covers four key terms: self-determination, human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding. Self-determination is the core search term, with the remaining terms categorized as essential supporting terms. These four keywords were arranged into progressively restrictive search criteria to provide a descriptive statistical picture of the literature available in prominent

academic databases and produce a final collection of articles that meet the criteria. The inclusion criteria are as follows

1. The final selected works must focus on self-determination, as this term is the core focus of the literature review.
2. Selected works must focus on the right to self-determination as articulated in UN Covenants and Declarations or the application of the right to self-determination within the context of those Covenants and Declarations.
3. The selected works must directly reference self-determination, human rights, and political economy. Peacebuilding was deemed desirable but not required because including this term yielded insufficient results to complete the review.

The search utilized the following progression. Step 5 was completed only with the JSTOR database due to the high volume of results remaining after step 4.

Figure 1: Progressive Search Protocol for Key Terms

The author conducted the search progression above across six academic databases: Scopus, EBSCO/OneSearch, ERIC, PubMed, UN Digital Library, and JSTOR. Search results were filtered to include only journal articles. Due to the large volume of search results from the JSTOR database, they were further limited to the subjects of international relations and peace

and conflict studies. The outcomes of this search progression for each database are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Results from Progressive Search of Academic Databases

Progression	SCOPUS	EBSCO	ERIC	PubMed	UN Digital Library	JSTOR
Self-determination	30,620	170,793	14,140	3,873	11,215	253939
Self-determination AND human rights	1629	15,394	177	1,973	5277	82729
Self-determination AND political economy	216	708	17	311	27	73345
Self-determination AND peacebuilding	22	36	1	0	96	661
Human rights AND political economy	2579	1097	40	3205	124	161706
Human rights AND peacebuilding	434	997	6	19	1939	2691
Political Economy and Peacebuilding	171	408	2	10	15	1909
Self-determination AND human rights AND political economy	7	130	4	245	15	35822
Self-determination AND human rights AND political economy AND peacebuilding	0	1	0	0	0	357
Self-determination AND human rights AND political Economy AND Peacebuilding (limited to international relations and peace and conflict studies) (134) Results						134

As a result of the initial progressive database search, 535 articles were identified for further review, as detailed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Articles selected for further review after the initial progressive search process.

SCOPUS	EBSCO	ERIC	PubMed	UN Digital Library	JSTOR
7	130	4	245	15	134
Total articles identified for further review					535

Following the initial progressive search, the author reviewed the titles and abstracts of the 535 identified articles to determine whether they included the key terms. For the Scopus database results, seven articles were reviewed, and one was selected for further review. A review of the EBSCO database identified 130 articles, leading to the inclusion of an additional 14. One of these articles contained all four search terms and was automatically included in the final collection of articles for the literature review. Four articles from the Eric database were reviewed, with none meeting the selection criteria. Likewise, 245 articles from PubMed and 15 from the UN digital library were reviewed, with none meeting the selection criteria. Finally,

134 titles from JSTOR were reviewed, with 1 article meeting the minimum criteria for inclusion. This secondary review of article titles and abstracts identified 17 articles for enhanced review. An enhanced review was then conducted on 17 articles, which involved searching the full texts of the identified articles for the core search term self-determination, followed by searches for the secondary required terms human rights and political economy, and the preferred but not required term peacebuilding. This search reduced the total number of articles eligible for inclusion in the study from 17 to 5. Table 3 outlines the five articles selected for final inclusion in the systemic mapping review below.

Table 3: Articles Selected for Review and Analysis

Author	Title	Citation	Source
Dobinson, T., Gower, G., & Fahey-Palma, T.	Anthropogenic impacts of mining on indigenous peoples in Western Australia: Divergent values.	Dobinson, T., Gower, G., & Fahey-Palma, T. (2024). Anthropogenic impacts of mining on indigenous peoples in Western Australia: Divergent values. <i>Ethnicities</i> , 24(4), 635–655. https://doi.org/10.1177/14687968231219582	EBSCO
Fernando, J. L.	The Political Economy of Post-War Reconstruction in Sri Lanka: Development-Security Nexus vs. Tamil Right to Self-Determination.	Fernando, J. L. (2017). The Political Economy of Post-War Reconstruction in Sri Lanka: Development-Security Nexus vs. Tamil Right to Self-Determination. <i>Asian Journal of Peacebuilding</i> , 5(1), 21–48. https://doi.org/10.18588/201705.00a024	EBSCO
Gamu, J. K., & Soendergaard, N.	Governance capture and socio-environmental conflict: A critical political economy of the global mining industry's prior consultation regime.	Gamu, J. K., & Soendergaard, N. (2024). Governance capture and socio-environmental conflict: A critical political economy of the global mining industry's prior consultation regime. <i>Review of International Political Economy</i> , 31(3), 880–904. https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2023.2265976	EBSCO
Ikeanyibe, O. M., Ugwu, C. E., Nzekwe, I. F., & Obioji, J.	The United Nations, the Political Economy of International Organisations, and Managing Self-Determination Struggles in Africa.	Ikeanyibe, O. M., Ugwu, C. E., Nzekwe, I. F., & Obioji, J. (2021). The United Nations, the Political Economy of International Organisations, and Managing Self-Determination Struggles in Africa. <i>International Journal of African Renaissance Studies - Multi-, Inter- and Transdisciplinarity</i> , 16(1), 123–148. https://doi.org/10.1080/18186874.2021.1950558	EBSCO
Rosch, R.	A New Era of Customary Property Rights? – Liberia's Land and Forest Legislation in Light of the Indigenous Right to Self-Determination.	Rosch, R. (2019). A New Era of Customary Property Rights? – Liberia's Land and Forest Legislation in Light of the Indigenous Right to Self-Determination. <i>Verfassung Und Recht in Übersee / Law and Politics in Africa, Asia, and Latin America</i> , 52(4), 439–462.	JSTOR

Findings

Summary Review and Critique of Selected Literature

This review begins with a summary and critique of the selected literature and then synthesizes key themes across the body of literature. The selected articles are examined in alphabetical order by first author's.

Article One

The first article, *Anthropogenic Impacts of Mining on Indigenous Peoples in Western Australia: Divergent Values* by Dobinson et al. (2024) analyzes the indigenous people's pursuit of self-determination in Western Australia through the lens of their inclusion in land rights decisions related to mining contracts and access. The authors adopt a narrative approach to explore Indigenous experiences with land rights by examining "yarns" told by one of the co-authors, an Indigenous community member (Dobinson et al., 2024, p. 640). These yarns revealed Indigenous communities' experiences of public and political disregard for the social, cultural, and ecological impacts of mining projects. Public officials focused on the economic value of the mining projects to fund state programs and provide employment. They narrated major projects as having "an [ecological] impact as small as a thumb prick or pinprick (Dobinson et al., 2024, p. 642)."

The research reveals deep divides in cultural and social values where mining companies and government processes prioritize revenue growth through the extraction of resources, and Indigenous communities prioritize ecological integrity, cultural traditions, and the "ensoulment of nature (pp. 635 - 644)." The narrative that emerges from "yarns" and supporting evidence documents significant disregard and disrespect for the rights of the Indigenous community on behalf of the mining companies and government, who view the communities as a hindrance in the process of obtaining access to the minerals they need and deserve. It also documents the relative ineffectiveness of the "social license to operate framework" implemented to protect Indigenous rights. Overall, Dobinson et al. (2024) paint a bleak yet hopeful picture of the status of Indigenous rights in Australia, with hope arising from successful efforts by Indigenous groups to prevent the full implementation of these projects.

Dobinson et al. (2024) craft a compelling narrative that frames the battle between governments, corporations, and Indigenous groups over the aggressive expansion of resource extraction and the land and property rights of Indigenous communities. The description of colonial attitudes and practices provides an appropriate background and historical context to the conflict, exemplified in the following quote.

Native Title was recognized by the Australian High Court in 1993 through the Mabo decision in 1992. Prior to this, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander claims for land rights were ignored on the premise that Australia belonged to no one when settlers arrived (Dobinson et al., 2024, p. 437).

The authors argue that, despite the change mentioned above to the legal framework, these attitudes regarding Indigenous self-determination, land ownership, and belonging still permeate government and corporate approaches to resource extraction. While the article excellently portrays the deep-seated conflicts over land and mineral rights, critiques the social license-to-operate system, and highlights violations of Indigenous human rights, it fails to offer a meaningful path forward. This failure is due in part to the non-binding nature of social licensing and safeguarding guidelines and procedures, and more significantly to the immense challenges posed by the political economy of resource extraction and the considerable monetary benefits at stake for governments and corporations. The authors adopt an idealist philosophy that advocates for the absolute sovereignty of Indigenous communities over their traditional lands. While this is absolutely an ideal worth striving for, it ignores the need for realist approaches to addressing the mass of systemic factors stacked against Indigenous communities, factors steeped in colonial legacies and deeply embedded in the fabric of modern society.

Article Two

Fernando (2017) examines self-determination, human rights, and political economy in the context of Sri Lanka and the Tamil quest for independence.

The Political Economy of Post-War Reconstruction in Sri Lanka: Development-Security Nexus vs. Tamil Right to Self-Determination by Jude la Fernando (2017) investigates the implementation and effects of international development efforts following the Civil War in Sri Lanka. Fernando unpacks the role of international superpowers in the economic, political, and cultural marginalization of the Tamil community in Sri Lanka as they competed for influence and control over the strategically located island. Fernando describes the considerable support that was provided to the Sinhala majority government to help them marginalize and eradicate the Tamil self-determination movement through militarized social, cultural, and economic responses in violation of the Tamils' human rights and right to self-determination. Fernando argues that the Tamil self-determination movement was sacrificed by global powers to secure a critical strategic geographic and political ally in the contest for dominance over the global

balance of security and stability, and to ensure stability and dominance of the Sinhala majority's political economy.

The article also asserts that the individual nature of universal human rights frameworks has severely limited Tamil avenues for recourse and access to remedies for human rights violations, forcing them to be adjudicated on a case-by-case basis rather than acknowledging the collective rights of the Tamil community.

Fernando (2017) argues that this individualization of human rights enforcement negates the collective rights of the people group, leaving them no meaningful avenue to secure justice for the violent oppression and extermination of their community in Sri Lanka.

Fernando's (2017) work is a compelling examination of the Tamil plight in Sri Lanka. It provides a powerful, well-articulated argument for the intersection of self-determination, human rights, and political economy frameworks, demonstrating the immense challenges peacebuilders face in resolving self-determination conflicts. Fernando's work highlights that peacebuilders must reconcile the intricacies of self-determination demands and access to individual and collective human rights with the broader political, economic, social, and cultural forces at play in the national and international political economy, including the violation of those rights. Peacebuilders must do more than understand and mediate the struggle between conflicting ideologies; they must be able to map the playing field and understand the larger forces at play in a local or national conflict situation.

Article Three

The third article explores another aspect of mineral rights and mining conflicts, focusing on Brazil and Peru. *Governance capture and socio-environmental conflict: A critical political economy of the global mining industry's prior consultation regime* by Gamu and Soendergaard (2024) examines the political economy of mineral resource mining, attempts to mandate the inclusion of local communities in decisions related to mineral extraction projects, and the outcomes of these schemes in the development and approval process of "mega-mining" projects in Brazil and Peru (Gamu & Soendergaard, 2024, p. 3). The authors argue that the mineral mining approval process amounts to a socio-political regime whose outcomes affect "collective identities, cultural practices, and livelihoods" and cause "economic, social, and ontological harms (Gamu & Soendergaard, 2024, p. 6)." The research explores the mechanisms underlying these project approval regimes and their impacts.

The primary mechanism explored is FPIC (Free, Prior, and Informed Consent), which requires governments to engage with communities about the project, its benefits, and its risks

to obtain approval before authorizing it. The challenge is determining how to obtain consent and what constitutes a legitimate measurement of the community's will. Is a majority decision sufficient? Or is a more comprehensive and unanimous expression of community agreement necessary to proceed with the project? While there is an assumption that communities have “veto powers,” their will can be superseded by the “public good (Gamu & Soendergaard, 2024, p. 7)” The authors describe a project development system that is stacked against local and Indigenous communities in favor of the corporations, the central government, and national elites who stand to profit the most from the projects. Manipulations of the system and lack of avenues for redress violate the human rights of the local communities most affected, leaving them little recourse outside of protest and violence to ensure their voices are heard.

The included case studies highlight the high-dimensional complexity surrounding large-scale mining projects. Political, economic, social, cultural, environmental, religious, and climate factors are at play, along with many additional subfactors that create a range of intersection points where competing value systems collide and ignite conflict. The immense demand for minerals worldwide to fuel continual economic growth and satisfy governments, corporations, and investors who value wealth creation collide with local communities' more complex and nuanced value set, making peaceful solutions difficult to envision and even more challenging to achieve.

Article Four

The fourth article examines the role of the United Nations in mediating and negotiating self-determination demands in Africa. *The United Nations, the Political Economy of International Organisations, and Managing Self-Determination Struggles in Africa*, by Ikeanyibe et al. (2021), explores United Nations (UN) responses to self-determination conflicts and advocates the development of more proactive response frameworks to prevent violence in such conflicts in Africa. The authors argue that the international community engages in “conspiratorial silence and non-action” when self-determination demands and conflicts emerge. They further describe Africa as a continent of “poly-communal and poly-normative” states heavily shaped by colonization (Ikeanyibe et al., 2021, p. 124). In the eyes of the authors, despite the UN’s focus on security, the lack of proactive and early intervention approaches to self-determination conflicts often results in elevated risks and occurrences of violence, adversely affecting vulnerable populations. The lack of proactive approaches is said to originate from a lack of clarity regarding what self-determination rights are supported, specifically, if the right to self-determination allows for the secession of a group from a nation-

state or if that aspect of the right has, for the most part, expired in the decades following the post-colonial reorganization of the international order following World War II. If this has indeed essentially expired, groups pursuing self-determination are then left to pursue greater autonomy through domestic processes.

Ikeanyibe et al. (2021) argue that the extreme violence that occurs between oppressive governments and marginalized ethnic groups currently pursuing self-determination has more dire consequences than the oppression that occurred under colonial rule and that many of these current conflicts result from the reorganization of Africa at the close of the colonial period. The imposed reorganization of separate ethnic groups into nation-states that fit within the ideal international framework for international relations is then instrumental in creating violent self-determination conflicts through forced proximity and nation-state development via aggregation. These authors argue that prioritizing maintaining the unity and integrity of African nation-states and limiting aggression and conflict between nations has resulted in limited engagement in intranational conflicts. Their description of the national and regional dynamics within the continent and their advocacy for an enhanced liberal institutional approach by the UN highlight the different ideologies and approaches that originate in the separate peace paradigms of realism and liberalism.

While Ikeanyibe et al. (2021) build a lengthy and well-resourced argument for enhancing and expanding liberal peacebuilding approaches to self-determination conflicts in Africa, their arguments for the failure of post-colonial geopolitical solutions and the incredible harm that results from international influence over political geography are also the strongest arguments against their proposed solution. The authors propose a solution of early and (United Nations Security Council, 2004) extensive intervention into self-determination conflicts in Africa and attempt to double down on the international interventions that will likely repackage solutions aligned with the international security values created by post-colonial international political geography solutions. Solutions that initially created the current geopolitical framework and disregard for ethnic relationships. The chosen case studies examine conflicts that lasted decades in Eritrea, Sudan, and Somalia, highlighting the eventual success of these secession movements and suggesting that earlier implementation of a framework for democratic resolution of the conflicts could have prevented the considerable loss of life. While this idea has gained popularity and potential merit, it is far from guaranteed. While technically on the list of successful secession movements, the case of South Sudan cannot be considered a successful case study for reducing violence. South Sudan experienced an extended civil war

from 2013 to 2020, shortly after it seceded from Sudan in 2011, resulting in the deaths of more than 400,000 people and the displacement of millions more (United States Holocaust Memorial Museum, 2024). As of the drafting of this article in November of 2024, Sudan, from which South Sudan seceded, is embroiled in a newer iteration of civil war that is displacing millions and causing thousands of needless deaths through violence, starvation, and disease (Zane & Ross, 2024). Despite decades of UN intervention in Sudan and South Sudan, these efforts have done little to quell the intense, recurring ethnic conflicts that flare up again and again.

Furthermore, Ikeanyibe et al. (2021, p. 138) argue for the violation of territorial sovereignty to prevent human rights violations and violence against vulnerable and oppressed communities because “Sovereignty has no meaning without people’s rights.” While this is an admirable ideological claim, it contradicts the precedent set by countless UN Security Council Resolutions that affirm the United Nations commitment to nation-state sovereignty and territorial integrity, exemplified by the following statement from a resolution on the conflict in Sudan from 2004, “Reaffirming its commitment to the sovereignty, unity, independence, and territorial integrity of Sudan and recalling the importance of the principles of good-neighborliness, non-interference, and regional cooperation (United Nations Security Council, 2004).”

Additionally, the authors argue that “suppression or repression of ... self-determination struggles” has rarely led to these groups abandoning their pursuit of autonomy (Ikeanyibe et al., 2021, p. 140). Again, while the claim has validity, there is another competing reality: achievement of self-determination by one group does not necessarily result in the peaceful resolution of intrastate conflict, as evidenced by the discussion of the case study of South Sudan above, which experienced an extended civil war on the heels of a successful self-determination campaign.

In his book *Identity: The Demand for Dignity and the Politics of Resentment*, Francis Fukuyama (2018) alludes to the reality that identity conflicts often subdivide rather than resolve.

“Individuals throughout human history have found themselves at odds with their societies. But only in modern times has the view taken hold that the authentic inner self is intrinsically valuable, and that outer society systematically misvalues the former. It is not the inner self that has to be made to conform to society’s rules, but society itself that needs to change (Fukuyama, 2018, p. 10).”

Though Fukuyama describes individual demands of identity recognition, the same applies to groups who feel disrespected and marginalized. The pursuit of societal change is not limited to one legitimately disenfranchised group. Instead, it can initiate a chain reaction in which smaller and smaller groups bring their grievances forward as preceding movements are either successful or extinguished by the majority. Additionally, Fukuyama argues that systems and political solutions have limits in their power to solve conflicts because these conflicts are, at the core, intensely human and personal. “People understand their circumstances as the fault of guilty and less deserving people, not as the product of broad social, economic, and political forces (Fukuyama, 2018, p. 72).” While Ikeanyibe et al. (2021) make a passionate case for early intervention to save lives and reduce violence, their proposed solution ignores the reality of human nature. Furthermore, the case studies suffer from tunnel vision about what could have been, while neglecting the considerable evidence that improved timing and the decisive use of international force oversimplify the immense complexity of self-determination conflicts and the political economy of peoples and nations that drive them.

Article Five

The fifth and final article explores land and forest rights legislation in Liberia. *A New Era of Customary Property Rights? – Liberia’s Land and Forest Legislation in Light of the Indigenous Right to Self-Determination* by Ricarda Rosch (2019) analyzes customary property rights in Liberia through the lens of the Indigenous right to self-determination. The author’s review of the Indigenous right to self-determination quickly equates it to the academic concept of internal self-determination. This connection is supported by the African Charter’s recognition of Indigenous self-determination, which does not conflict with the sovereignty of state territories and borders. They further highlight the ambiguity of the UN definitions of Indigenous people and the lack of clear criteria for establishing Indigenous status (Rosch, 2019).

Like many nations worldwide, Liberia was deeply affected by colonization. The expansion of settler rights and the subsequent elimination of customary property rights led to the reversion of “undeeded land” to the public domain, affecting many local communities, especially those native to the land who may or may not identify as Indigenous (Rosch, 2019, p. 445). While cultural identities may not lead to self-identification of groups as Indigenous, the lack of explicit self-identification does not preclude their rights. At the same time, the rights available to Indigenous groups are also driving the adoption of Indigenous identification as a “strategy.” Despite the origins of Indigenous identities in Liberia, Rosch demonstrates that

Indigenous-identifying communities and other “communities affected by the law” were not adequately included in the drafting of Liberia’s customary rights law, with populations from the rural interior of the country largely excluded from the process (Rosch, 2019, p. 447). Rosch describes a normative, majority- and elite-centric approach to developing legislation, supported by international agencies and actors, in which a “donor-funded consultant” drafted the final legislation.

Rosch (2019) highlights that the communities at the supposed heart of the legislation's purpose were excluded because inclusion was impractical. It was impractical for logistical reasons (cost, travel difficulty, lack of legal and legislative background, and knowledge) and conceptual reasons. According to Barbara Johnson (1986) it is easier to “apostrophe” a person or group if they are not present to object or contradict the preferred narrative. She describes the process of apostrophe as “the direct address of the absent, dead, or inanimate being by a first-person speaker,” “a form of ventriloquism through which the speaker throws voice, life, and human form into the addressee, turning its silence into a mute responsiveness.” The discussion of the legislative process paints a picture of symbolic inclusion of Indigenous rights, but with ‘appropriate’ loopholes that allow the state and elite interests to continue to profit from the land and its resources, while appearing to grant some measure of self-determination to Indigenous groups (Rosch, 2019). The article provides another solid example of the complexity of the political, economic, cultural, and social factors that motivate and enable the manipulation of the political economy by self-interested or even political groups that identify as altruistic.

Discussion

Synthesis of Key Themes Across the Articles

The preceding review of each selected piece of literature on self-determination, human rights, and political economy reveals the following themes.

Table 4: Themes Identified in Selected Articles

Article	Theme
Anthropogenic impacts of mining on indigenous peoples in Western Australia: Divergent values. (Dobinson et al., 2024)	State and corporate interests undermine indigenous human and self-determination rights for extractive purposes.
The Political Economy of Post-War Reconstruction in Sri Lanka: Development-Security Nexus vs. Tamil Right to Self-Determination. (Fernando, 2017)f	Global political economy and security concerns supersede human and self-determination rights.
Governance capture and socio-environmental conflict: A critical political economy of the global mining industry’s prior consultation regime. (Gamu & Soendergaard, 2024)	State and corporate interests undermine indigenous human and self-determination rights for extractive purposes.

The United Nations, the Political Economy of International Organisations, and Managing Self-Determination Struggles in Africa. (Ikeanyibe et al., 2021)	The article calls for neo-colonial international intervention in self-determination conflicts to protect human rights despite its critiques of colonialism’s negative impact.
Property Rights? – Liberia’s Land and Forest Legislation in Light of the Indigenous Right to Self-Determination. (Rosch, 2019)	Powerful actors manipulate legislation development to sustain domination and extraction, impacting the self-determination rights of Indigenous and local communities.

Three themes emerge across the selected literature pieces that reveal the global and local challenges to self-determination rights and the potential for these conflicts to amplify their intensity. The first emergent theme is the profound disparity in priorities between self-determination rights holders, national and international governments, and multinational corporations. Second is the idea of domination for extraction, in which the priorities of conflicting parties are misaligned, and the powerful engage in practices of domination to maintain their ability to extract the resources they desire. Third is the lack of clarity about the best approach to resolving these conflicts, with advocacy for neo-colonial international intervention dominating an entire article and detailed descriptions of the failures of the mandatory consultation framework and processes dominating other articles. These themes suggest that the global community either does not fully understand the complexity of self-determination rights and related conflicts or lacks the will and discipline to uphold the frameworks and standards established through international declarations and covenants.

Disparities in Priorities

The literature reveals a profound disparity in priorities among stakeholders, with nation-states, multinational corporations, and international bodies operating under the assumption that their path to progress is inevitable. In the case studies on minerals in Australia, Brazil, and Peru, mining projects are viewed as inevitable, with FPIC and SLA consultations treated as mere formalities that cause delays that must be endured to achieve economic goals. They assume that all parties desire the project and that consultations are merely negotiations over how it will be implemented; after all, the revenue from extractive projects will support service delivery and ensure access to core human rights. In Liberia, it is assumed that land rights and community forest regulations should be negotiated based on the collective needs of the country and in accordance with the recently established precedent that reverts untitled land to national ownership. This assumes that rationality and logic are inevitable and will ultimately result in extractivist outcomes, framed as public goods, despite disparities in benefits across stakeholders. These assumptions and expectations marginalize the voices of rights holders and

erode their ability to shape their political, economic, cultural, and social futures. The disregard for their voices creates a disproportionate distribution of risk to affected communities and a lack of pathways for rights holders to hold governments and multinational corporations accountable for adverse outcomes of these projects, which often violate the self-determination rights of Indigenous or minority groups. Furthermore, the disparities in priorities ultimately create a context ripe for domination, where powerful actors exploit their position to achieve their goals.

Domination for Extraction

The case studies discussed in the literature highlight that domination emerges as a mechanism through which powerful actors maintain control and extract resources, often using institutionalized processes. Fernando's (2017) article details the desecration of Tamil self-determination rights in Sri Lanka for the prosperity of the Sri Lankan Sinhala majority and 'global security' benefits to international superpowers. His exposition of the power dynamics that shaped the annihilation and oppression of the Tamil self-determination movement creates the impetus for deep reflection on Ikeanyibe et al.'s (2021) solution of early international intervention, including violations of territorial sanctity to prevent violence and loss of life. While international military forces did not violate Sri Lankan territory, according to Fernando, they did play a significant role in helping the Sinhalese government violently suppress the Tamil self-determination movement. International disregard for the sanctity of Tamil self-determination claims and disrespect for the communities involved allows for the pursuit of strategic alliances for political and military collaboration and Sinhalese extraction of land rights and economic opportunities from the Tamil people, increasing their dominance over the Tamils. This disregard for Tamil rights highlights how international actors, using the need for strategic alliances and enhanced security as leverage, can contribute to the exploitation and marginalization of minority groups.

Domination is also a vital aspect of the case studies presented in the literature on mining projects in Western Australia, Brazil, and Peru, as well as in the development of land rights legislation in Liberia. In the mining case studies, the perception that mining projects were inevitable led to the co-opting of consultation and consent processes with local stakeholders. In Liberia, the maximization of the conversion of untitled land into publicly owned land negates the customary and land-use rights of local indigenous and indigenous-identifying populations. Land rights are also an issue in the Australian mining case, where the authors identified a fundamental assumption regarding land ownership: "Australia belonged to no one when

settlers arrived (Dobinson et al., 2024, p. 437)” Dobinson's capture of this critical assumption summarizes the failure of governments and the international community to understand the dominance inherent in their assumptions about extraction rights. The resulting domination perpetuates conflicts and underscores the complexities in determining the best approach to resolving them. These forms of domination highlight the challenges of addressing disparities in priorities and reveal why potential solutions such as international intervention remain highly contentious. These examples illustrate the co-option of consultative processes to maintain extractive practices despite local and indigenous claims to land and resources.

Lack of Viable Resolution Options

Scholars do not agree on the best approach to resolving these conflicts: some advocate for international intervention, while others highlight the inherent risks of such involvement. The article by Ikeanyibe et al. (2021), calling for early international intervention and violations of territorial sovereignty in self-determination conflicts to prevent violence and loss of life, is contrasted by Fernando's (2017) haunting recounting of the role of international superpowers in the demise of the Tamil self-determination movement and the deaths of 70,000 people. The violent elimination of the Tamil self-determination movement illustrates how existing power dynamics enhanced by international interests and competition can amplify sovereign and majority domination of minority groups, preventing the enjoyment of their self-determination and human rights.

The solution proposed by Ikeanyibe et al. (2021) invites further domination and manipulation by international players to achieve short-term gains in reducing violence through neocolonial practices sanctioned as humanitarian peacekeeping efforts. International prohibitions on interference in the domestic affairs of sovereign nations are in place because the inherent human tendencies toward imperial domination and neo-colonial practices are difficult, bordering on impossible, to eliminate. Furthermore, despite these prohibitions, international superpowers rarely hesitate to manipulate these situations to their advantage, as evidenced in Fernando's work on the plight of the Tamil people in Sri Lanka. The international track record of domination may prevent violence in the short term, but may have adverse consequences for groups pursuing self-determination, respect for their human rights, and control over their political economy. Similarly, the influence of multinational corporations and governments over the consultation processes designed to protect local and indigenous self-determination and land rights is equally problematic, yielding unreliable protections for self-determination and human rights. The failure of the international community to successfully

safeguard rights across the political, economic, cultural, and social spectrum of self-determination indicates that new approaches are needed to address the underlying differences in priorities, perceptions, and expectations that fuel conflict and thwart peacebuilding efforts.

To conclude, the identified themes—disparity of priorities, dominance for extraction, and lack of viable options to resolve these conflicts—illustrate the complexity of conflicts over self-determination rights. Addressing these challenges requires acknowledging the considerable power imbalances inherent in these conflicts and committing to pluralistic discourse and negotiations that set aside assumptions of inevitability and prioritize truly equitable outcomes.

Conclusion

While these articles employ a critical political economy approach that is essential for analyzing the embedded power imbalances and critiquing state and international approaches to the right to self-determination, other counterarguments also deserve consideration. The importance of international security, the necessity of extracting resources to fund development to deliver rights and services, and the nation-state's right to determine land use within its borders also have considerable validity and remain largely unaddressed by these articles. These counterarguments serve as a reminder that self-determination discourse must be pluralistic. Discussions and negotiations over the path forward must reconcile the reality that many potential paths exist and account for the needs and rights of all parties in pursuit of establishing new social contracts and balancing the sovereign equation.

This systematic literature review shows that self-determination cannot be meaningfully understood apart from human rights, political economy, and peacebuilding. Across the literature, struggles for self-determination emerge not only as disputes over political status but also as conflicts over dignity, resource control, inclusion, and the terms under which communities are permitted to shape their futures. The persistence of these tensions reveals that peacebuilding in self-determination conflicts requires more than procedural settlement or institutional management; it requires sustained engagement with the human rights claims, political economy structures, and power asymmetries that continue to drive domination, extraction, and exclusion.

Implications for Future Research

The analysis from this systematic literature review reveals that additional research is needed to explore pathways for aligning priorities and for openly communicating perceptions, assumptions, and expectations. Self-determination, as outlined in the United Nations

Declarations and Conventions, is understood to be a relatively recent concept with Western philosophical origins. However, this simplification of self-determination overlooks and sidelines the extensive global history of evolving governance practices across Eastern, Indigenous, and Western traditions, imperialist and colonial domination, and emerging technology-inspired governance structures that promise to shape the future of sovereignty, governance, and implementation of self-determination rights. A mapping of self-determination as a theory, practice, and field of study is needed to guide future research to inform peacebuilding efforts targeting self-determination conflicts.

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AI Usage Acknowledgement

For the final preparation of this work, the author employed ChatGPT 5.2 to improve the clarity and readability of the text. Following the utilization of this tool, the author thoroughly reviewed the content as necessary, assuming full responsibility for the publication's content.

Motivated Reasoning and the Decision-Making of Coup Resisters: Choosing to Leave or Stay in the Tanintharyi Region, Southern Myanmar

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ABSTRACT

Problem Statement	After the Myanmar military junta suppressed the nationwide anti-coup movement in February 2021, including in the Tanintharyi region of southern Myanmar, many coup resisters fled abroad due to security and survival concerns, while others chose to remain.
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) To identify the profiles of coup resisters. (2) To explore the psychological factors that influence the decision of coup resisters in Tanintharyi. (3) To explore the external factors that influence the decision of coup resisters and how psychological factors: personal beliefs, values, and attitudes, interact with them. (4) To examine coup resisters' perceptions of the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance and peacebuilding efforts.
Methods	This research was based on qualitative analysis using primary data sources collected through informal conversations with 24 coup resisters.
Findings	This research investigated psychological and social dynamics within the resistance movement. The study examined the role of psychological factors: personal beliefs, values, and attitudes, and the role of external factors, including family, community, and socioeconomic conditions, in the coup resisters' decision-making. It also examined how psychological factors interact with external factors to shape individual decisions through the lens of theories of motivated reasoning, decision-making, and cognitive dissonance.
Conclusion	The findings deepened understanding of social dynamics at play among Tanintharyi coup resisters and the perceived consequences of their choices for the broader resistance movement.
Keywords	Cognitive dissonance, Coup resisters, Decision-making, Motivated reasoning, Peacebuilding

INTRODUCTION

Background

After the Myanmar military coup in February 2021, the anti-coup movement rose nationwide, including in the Tanintharyi Region. In response, the Myanmar military brutally suppressed the movement by detaining, torturing, and extrajudicially killing the coup resisters. This climate of fear and violence forced many to flee abroad, while others chose to stay and resist within the country. A few months after the brutal crackdown, the political crisis turned into an armed conflict and spread across the country. Suppressions by the military junta have continued to intensify, with unlawful acts, including destroying civilian properties, burning villages, and airstrikes over civilian areas.

Four years after the coup, more than 6,000 people have been killed, and over 20,000 have been detained (Amnesty International, 2025). In addition, over 100,000 civilian homes had been destroyed. (Data for Myanmar, 2025). The crisis had affected all sectors, including education and health care. School enrollment has dropped, with over 20 % of children out of school in the 2023/2024 academic year. The worsening socioeconomic and security conditions have led to a large-scale forced migration. Approximately 3.5 million people have been internally displaced. 3.7 million have migrated to Thailand by 2023. Many of them face exploitation due to their lack of legal status (UN News, 2025).

All of these crises followed the same pattern and situation in the Tanintharyi region. In 2024 alone, over 600 armed clashes between the Myanmar military and the revolutionary forces, nearly 100 air strikes, and 70 drone attacks were conducted by the military junta in the Tanintharyi region. 50,000 to 70,000 people were internally displaced and returned every month. Due to the fluid nature of displacement, the number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) and returnees in the Tanintharyi region changes regularly.

In addition, the introduction of a conscription law by the military junta in February 2024 has further accelerated migration out of the region. Most of Tanintharyi's people have fled to Thailand and Malaysia due to geographic proximity to escape forced recruitment, violence, and socioeconomic crisis (FE5 Tanintharyi, 2025). All these crises: the armed conflict, forced displacement, political repression, and the worsening socioeconomic conditions, have led to an examination of how individuals, particularly coup resisters, make decisions to stay or leave.

Problem Statement

The decision to leave or stay in the country has led to social tension and misunderstanding among coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region, Southern Myanmar. These different choices have also created challenges to the unity and coordination within the anti-coup movement. This study investigated the psychological and external factors that shaped the decisions of coup resisters through the frameworks of motivated reasoning, cognitive dissonance, and decision-making theory. A deeper understanding of these influential factors and social dynamics is crucial for better cooperation within the resistance movement, future nation-building, and peacebuilding strategies.

Objectives

- (1) To identify the profiles of coup resisters.
- (2) To explore the psychological factors that influence the decision of coup resisters in Tanintharyi.
- (3) To explore the external factors that influence the decision of coup resisters and how psychological factors: personal beliefs, values, and attitudes, interact with them.
- (4) To examine coup resisters' perceptions of the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance and peacebuilding efforts.

Research Question

- (1) What is the profile of coup resisters?
- (2) What psychological factors influence the decision of coup resisters to join the movement and to leave or stay in Tanintharyi?
- (3) What external factors (security, family, friends, community, media/social media, personal experience, etc.) influence the decision of coup resisters to leave or stay in Tanintharyi, and how do psychological factors interact with them?
- (4) How do coup resisters perceive the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance and peacebuilding efforts?

METHODOLOGY

Scope, Limitation, and Delimitation

This section discusses the boundaries of the paper. The scope of the study is the psychological and social dynamics among coup resisters. It focuses on coup resisters from the Tanintharyi Region only, and was conducted through informal conversations during March-June 2025. And this research did not investigate the momentum and strategies of the anti-coup movement. It will not discuss the active roles of the armed and non-armed coup resisters. Please see **Figure 1** below.

Figure 1: Scope, Limitations, and Delimitations
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Literature Review

This literature review examines the decision-making processes of coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region of Myanmar by drawing on psychological theories and exploring the roles of personal beliefs, values, and attitudes. These concepts provide a lens to understand how coup resisters rationalize their choices to either remain in the country or flee, particularly under conditions of repression and armed conflict.

Coup Resisters

Coup resisters are the individuals or groups resisting Myanmar’s 2021 military coup. They are not only persons who actively joined the armed and non-armed struggle, but also civilians who expressed opposition to the military regime in various forms.

In this research, two terms of coup resisters have been used.

- (1) Domestic coup resisters refer to individuals who remain inside the country and resist.
- (2) Exile coup resisters refer to individuals who leave the country and resist.

Beliefs

Collins Dictionary (2025) defines belief as a feeling of certainty that something exists, is true, or is good. They serve as cognitive anchors in decision-making processes and shape how people interpret events, threats, and opportunities. For coup resisters, beliefs about justice, democracy, freedom, and the armed or non-armed struggle inform their choices.

Personal Values

Personal values refer to the core principles or standards of individuals. The principles are important in deciding what is right or wrong, acceptable or unacceptable in people's lives (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025). These values, such as fairness, courage, family, and royalty, often guide moral judgments and long-term commitments, influencing how individuals weigh the risks and consequences of resisting the military regime.

Attitudes

According to the Cambridge Dictionary (2025), an attitude is a way of thinking or behaving influenced by feelings or opinions. In the context of political resistance, attitudes toward the military, resistance groups, and socioeconomic conditions can significantly influence a person's willingness to engage in armed or non-armed movements and stay in the country or leave.

Motivated Reasoning Theory

This theory, introduced by Ziva Kunda (1990), explains how individuals align their beliefs with their desires, often justifying decisions that reflect their goals. For coup resisters, decisions to stay or leave are influenced by their attachments to political beliefs, personal values, and the climate of fear. Rather than seeking objective truth, people often justify decisions that align with their beliefs, personal values, and goals. For coup resisters, motivated reasoning may be used to rationalize the decision to stay or leave and to choose the way and strategy of their involvement in the movement based on attachment to political beliefs and social belonging.

Cognitive Dissonance Theory

Cognitive dissonance (Leon Festinger, 1957) occurs when individuals are confronted with facts that contradict their beliefs, values, and ideas. They will try to find a way to resolve the contradiction to reduce their discomfort. In political crisis environments, such as post-coup Myanmar, this dissonance can manifest in the internal conflict between the desire to resist authoritarian rule and the need to protect oneself or one’s family. Individuals often resolve this dissonance by changing their beliefs or reframing their decisions to maintain a sense of psychological comfort.

Decision-Making Theory

Simon’s (1947) decision-making theory (Unacademy, 2025; Antonius Alijoyo, 2021) explains that decisions involve selecting an option among different options and possibilities. It describes how people can make decisions within certain limits of available information, time, and cognitive capacity. People don’t always make perfectly logical decisions. They often choose options that are “good enough” rather than the best possible. In the case of coup resisters, decisions to stay or leave are made under extreme stress, uncertainty, and limited choices.

Together, these theories and concepts offer a valuable framework for understanding how coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region justify their actions in the face of moral dilemmas, political violence, and social pressure. They also help explain the variation in responses among coup resisters and the underlying factors shaping resistance directions.

Research Gap

Many studies have examined revolutionary momentum, various strategies of anti-coup movements: the armed and non-armed movements, the key actors: the State Administrative Council (SAC) of Myanmar, Ethnic Revolutionary Organizations (EROs), People Defense Forces (PDF), Political Organizations and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), the impacts of the conflict, such as social, economic, health, and education collapse, human rights violations, humanitarian, mental health. However, there is a lack of studies focusing on the psychological factors that influence individual decision-making. This gap limits a deeper understanding of the psychological and external factors that shape resistance behaviors and affect solidarity within the movement. Please see **Table 1** below.

Table 1: Research Questions and Theories

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RQ1 Profiles	Demographics
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RQ2: Psychological Factors	Cognitive dissonance, motivated reasoning, and Decision-making theories
RQ3: External Factors	Cognitive dissonance, motivated reasoning, and Decision-making theories
RQ4: Perception of Consequences	Cognitive dissonance, motivated reasoning, and decision-making theories

Research Methodology

This research was based on qualitative analysis by using primary sources of data, including informal conversations with coup resisters in the Tanintharyi Region. Employing the narratives, this research allows the exploration of psychological and external factors, personal narratives, and motivations that shape their decisions. The Index of Item Objectives Concurrence (IOC) for interview questions & the research questions was provided. Please see **Appendix (A)**.

Sampling

A purposive sampling method was used to select coup resisters. The sample size included 24 participants to ensure diversity in age, gender, experiences, and perspectives. They were categorized into three age groups: 25-35 (youths), 36-50 (adults), and 51-65 (senior adults).

Data Collection

There are two sources of data collection. The first is primary sources. The second is secondary sources. Primary sources include informal conversations. It was conducted via the Zoom platform and self-reports. The questions were translated from English to the Myanmar language. The secondary data sources include research articles, such as "The Case of Motivated Reasoning" by Ziva Kanda (1990), and "The Review of Cognitive Dissonance Theory and its Relevance to Current Social Issues" by Azizul Halim Yahya and Vidi Sukmayadi (2020), as well as media resources (Online Dictionary), which were utilized.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using thematic analysis. Themes include profiles, psychological factors, beliefs, values, attitudes, external factors, and perceptions of interviewees regarding the consequences of their decision to stay or leave.

Conceptual Framework

It is a conceptual framework of the study. Please see **Figure 2** below.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

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Benefits of the Study

The study contributes to a better understanding of the psychological and social dynamics within resistance movements in Tanintharyi, Southern Myanmar.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings 1

1. Profiles of Coup Resisters

1.1 Demographics of coup resisters

A total of 24 coup resisters participated in this research. 75% are male, and 25% are female. 75% are youth aged between 25 and 35 years old, 17% are adults aged between 36 and 50 years old, and 8% are senior adults aged between 51 and 65 years old. Among the participants, 54% held a university degree, while 46% had not yet completed university education. 79% of coup resisters live abroad, while 21% remain in the country.

79% of resisters are Buddhists, 17% are Atheists, and 4% are Agnostics. 79% had experience in advocacy or activism before the coup, while 21% had not. See **Figures 3 and 4** below.

Figure 3: % of interviewees and their religion
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EXPERIENCE IN ACTIVISM BEFORE THE COUP

Figure 4: % of interviewees and their experience in activism
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If it was classified by gender, 13 male and 6 female interviewees are Buddhist, 4 males are Atheist, and a male is Agnostic. 13 males have experience in activism before the coup, and 4 males didn't have. And 6 females didn't have. See **Tables 3 and 4** below.

Table 2: No. of males and females, and their religion
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Gender	Buddhist	Atheist	Agnostic
Male	13	4	1
Female	6	0	0

Table 3: No. of males and females and their experience in activism

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Gender	Have experience in activism before the coup	No experience in activism before the coup
Male	13	4
Female	6	0

The demographic details of the coup resisters' profile are provided. Please see **Appendix (B)**.

1.2 Life Before the Coup

According to the coup resisters from Tanintharyi, life before the coup was generally filled with peace, freedom, and hope for the future. In particular, the period from 2015 to 2020 was described as a time of relative freedom and the rule of law. People were able to move around freely even at midnight. The economy was functioning reasonably well, and there were opportunities for education and employment. Life was pleasant because people could make their own decisions, and they could speak and discuss openly and freely about whatever mattered to them.

1.3 Impact of the Coup

The military coup has negatively affected the socioeconomic condition and individual mental health.

Economy

Businesses could no longer operate normally. There was high inflation, and the prices of goods skyrocketed. Before the coup, the exchange rate was over 1,300 Kyats per USD, but more than

four years later, it rose to over 4,000 Kyats per USD. On the other hand, income levels dropped due to the collapse of business activity and the lack of employment opportunities.

Social Life

Many families were separated and displaced. Because the military targeted not only those directly involved in the resistance but also their family members, many had to relocate for safety reasons. In particular, after a conscription law was announced in February 2024, many young people fled from their hometowns. Family planning and long-term plans were often put on hold.

Among domestic coup resisters, there were three groups:

1. Those who stayed in their hometowns acted as if they were involved in nothing.
2. Those who relocated to other regions or towns within the country.
3. Those who fled to liberated areas and became actively involved in armed resistance in various capacities. See Figure 5 below.

Figure (5) Groups of domestic coup resisters
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Changes in Community Life

Most schools remain closed, especially in rural areas, and local businesses struggle to operate effectively.

Due to declining economic conditions and limited job opportunities, many people have migrated to neighboring countries, such as Thailand and Malaysia, to work as migrant laborers. Those who had previously returned from Thailand to resettle in their hometowns before the coup have shut down their businesses and gone back to Thailand. Others who were planning to return can no longer do so. The enactment of a conscription law has pushed the remaining youth out of the country, forcing them to flee.

As most youth have fled their hometowns, villages are now primarily populated by elders. Local community activities have weakened because the youth who were the main drivers of community activities have departed. Festivals and traditional ceremonies are no longer held as they once were.

In villages closer to towns or among wealthier families, some children continue their education in private schools. Public hospitals and clinics can no longer function properly, and people live in constant fear of clashes or airstrikes. Freedom of speech has been lost, and in social life, there is growing mistrust among individuals, leading to strained relationships.

The groups with ties to the military gain more privileges and opportunities to conduct business. All these issues affected an individual's psychological well-being.

Psychological Impacts

Due to the collapse of everything and the constant state of anxiety, there have been significant psychological impacts. Because family members are scattered in different places, people experience worry and distress. Living with constant worry and insecurity also affects family and social relationships. Whenever a family member goes out, those left behind live in anxious anticipation until they return safely.

“After the coup, everyone was put in a cage. To speak frankly, it's like we've all been imprisoned in some way. I can only move around within a small area where I'm currently staying.”

- Interviewee No. I007-25, Domestic coup resister, Buddhist, 38-year-old male, from Launglone Township, Tanintharyi Region

It is a summary of **Funding 1**. Please see **Table 4** below.

Table 4: Summary of Finding 1
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Research Question no.	Finding
RQ 1.1 Demographic	The majority of the coup resisters are young and stay abroad.
RQ 1.2 Life before the coup (2015-2020)	Life was generally filled with peace, freedom, hope, and the rule of law. The economy was functioning well, and there were opportunities for education and employment under civilian leadership.
RQ 1.3 Impact of the coup	<p>Socioeconomic conditions</p> <p>The economy declined. Local businesses struggle to operate. Most schools remain closed. Many families were separated and displaced. The 2024 conscription law led many youths to flee their hometowns. Local community has weakened. Freedom of speech lost, social mistrust increased. The groups with ties to the military gain more privileges and opportunities to conduct business.</p> <p>Psychological conditions</p> <p>People live in a state of fear due to repression, clashes, or airstrikes. Constant worry and insecurity negatively affect family and social cohesion.</p>

Findings 2

2. Psychological factors influencing the decisions of coup resisters

2.1 Coup resisters' perceptions toward the Military Junta

Coup resisters in this study perceived the military and its authoritarian rule as brutal and inhumane. They viewed the military as a self-serving institution that prioritizes personal or group interests over national interests. It saw itself as the savior of the nation and ruled through fear while attempting to control every aspect of life. The military is also viewed as religiously extremist.

“Their institution is fundamentally wrong. We must deconstruct it. Their ideology is clear: this country must be Buddhist, and the rulers must be Burmese.”

- Interviewee No. I002-25, Exile coup resister, Agnostic, Male, 34 years old, Dawei, Tanintharyi

2.2 Coup resisters' perceptions toward the Resistance Movement

Although there was no disagreement among participants regarding the value of resistance, they expressed concern when individuals or organizations from both armed and non-armed movements engaged in the following:

1. Becoming authoritarian while fighting against authoritarianism.
2. Suppressing fellow resistance members and violating human rights.
3. Exploiting the resistance for personal gain in terms of money or power.
4. A loss of humanity and empathy.
5. Failure to achieve unity among resistance actors, both armed and non-armed movements.
6. Labeling those with differing views as enemies or siding with the military.

“There are ideological differences in politics among the coup-resister groups. I’ve researched coup resisters. Sometimes, they even show authoritarian behavior. When I realized that, I began to question the idea that resisting authoritarianism always means you are not authoritarian yourself.”

- Interviewee No. I019-25, Exile coup resister, Buddhist, Female, 22 years old, Dawei, Tanintharyi

Some coup resisters also expressed doubt due to the lack of visible progress and the negative consequences of armed and non-armed struggle, including the political formation for the future of Tanintharyi. These factors led them to become skeptical of resistance and the idea of defeating military rule through armed and non-armed resistance.

2.3 Motivations involved in the anti-coup movement

Coup resisters in this study reported that the following psychological factors drove their participation in resisting authoritarianism:

1. A desire to reclaim democracy, freedom, and justice.
2. A sense of standing on the side of truth.
3. A feeling of moral obligation, especially as they saw people younger than themselves taking up arms.

4. A refusal to return to the military dictatorship period: it is before 2010, when the military junta allowed the wealthy and powerful to do things without justice.
5. A desire to prevent future generations from experiencing the underdevelopment caused by military rule. See **Figure 6** below.

Figure (6): Motivations involved in the anti-coup movement
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2.4 Motivations behind the decision to stay or leave

Exile coup resisters said personal values or beliefs did not primarily influence their decision. The external factors are most influential in their departure.

On the other hand, domestic coup resisters expressed a deep desire to be actively involved in the revolution and to avoid being separated from the ground and their families.

“If I leave the country, it will feel like I’ve stepped away from the armed revolution. If we all left, then who would fight this armed revolution and make it successful? I believe the revolution exists on the ground. So I’ve decided to stay in this land, with these people, and join the resistance to free them.”

- Interviewee No. I023-25, Domestic coup resister, Atheist, Male, 23 years old, Dawei, Tanintharyi

It is a summary of Finding 2. Please see **Table 5** below.

Table 5: Summary of Finding 2
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Research question no.	Finding
2.1 Coup resisters' perceptions toward the Military Junta	Brutal, inhumane, and self-serving institution. Religious extremists,
2.2 Coup resisters' perceptions toward the Resistance Movement	No disagreement regarding the value of the resistance. But concerns about actions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Becoming authoritarian - Suppressing fellow resistance members - Violating human rights - Exploiting the resistance for personal gains - Lack of unity and visible progress - No progress in the political formation for the future of Tanintharyi
2.3 Motivations involved in the anti-coup movement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desire to reclaim democracy, freedom, and justice - Standing on the side of truth - Moral obligation - Commitment to refuse the underdevelopment caused by military rule.
2.4 Motivations behind the decision to stay or leave	<p>Domestic Coup Resisters Political belief, values, and a deep desire to be actively involved in the revolution and to avoid being separated from the ground and their families.</p> <p>Exile Coup Resisters The external factors are most influential in their departure to go abroad.</p>

Findings 3

3.1 External factors influenced the decision to stay or leave Tanintharyi

Although both domestic and exile coup resisters faced similar security concerns, their responses and decisions differed. Among exile coup resisters, security was found to be the most influential factor in their decision, followed by personal experience as the second most significant, and friends as the third. Family influence came fourth, while community and media/social media had the least influence. See the table (6) below.

Table 6: Influential factors on exile coup resisters leaving the country
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Influential Factor	Security	Family	Friend	Community	Media/ social media	Personal Experience
Numbers of resister	18	9	13	7	7	15

In contrast, domestic coup resisters also faced pressure from security risks and other forms of stress. However, they actively sought ways to remain and continue their involvement. Their decision to stay was primarily driven by their values on family, family situation, and the nature of their work to be physically present and involved in the movement on the ground. See the table (7) below.

Table 7: Influential factors on domestic coup resisters remaining in the country
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Influential Factor	Security	Family	Friend	Community	Media/ Social Media	Personal Experience
Number of resisters	0	3	0	0	0	0

“The most important thing is that the work I do requires me to see and hear things firsthand. I believe that brings me closer to the truth. If I live abroad, how will I cover the news? Would I be able to work freely?”

- Interviewee No. I024-25, Domestic coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 37 years old, Launglone, Tanintharyi

3.2 How do personal beliefs, values, and attitudes interact with external factors

Both exile and domestic coup resisters demonstrated an awareness of the external and internal factors influencing their decisions, as reflected in their responses.

However, the interactions between psychological factors (personal beliefs, values, and attitudes) and the external factors (security, family, personal experiences, friends, etc.) were not clearly articulated by most coup resisters. And some were not even consciously aware of this interaction between psychological factors and external factors in their decision-making process.

"Other than wanting to leave, I didn't really think deeply about anything else. I didn't have any special or serious thoughts."

- Interviewee No. I003-25, Exile coup resister, Atheist, Male, 24 years old, Myeik, Tanintharyi

It is a summary of Finding 3. Please see **Table 8** below.

Table 8: Summary of Finding 3
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Research question no.	Findings
<p>3.1 External factors influenced the decision to stay or leave Tanintharyi</p>	<p>Although both domestic and exile coup resisters faced similar security concerns, their responses and decisions differed.</p> <p>Exile coup resisters Security, Personal experience, Friends, Community, Media/social media</p> <p>Domestic coup resisters Domestic coup resisters also faced pressure from security risks and other forms of stress from all directions. However, they decided to remain for their deep value on family life and participating in the movement on the ground physically.</p>
<p>3.2 How do your personal beliefs, values, and attitudes interact with the external factors?</p>	<p>The interactions between psychological factors and the external factors were not clearly articulated by most coup resisters. And some were not even consciously aware of it.</p>

Findings 4

4. The Perception of coup resisters on the consequences of their decisions for future peacebuilding

4.1 Social and psychological dynamics among the coup resisters

Divisions have existed between domestic and exile resisters. These groups often differ in their perspectives during discussions about resistance-related works. The coup resisters pointed out the following triggers:

“On ground” Vs. “On air”

Domestic resisters emphasized that real resistance must be grounded in the lived experiences of the people. They believed that being physically with people allows for a genuine understanding of the pain and the desire for peace. They argued that some emotional truths cannot be grasped from afar and must be felt with the heart. Domestic resisters often criticized those overseas, believing they lack understanding of on-the-ground realities. Some resisters noted that exile coup resisters sometimes express overly bold opinions.

In contrast, Many exile coup resisters believe they could better support the resistance once in a safer location. Some believe their skills are better utilized from abroad, including in logistic support, humanitarian aid, fundraising, and digital activism. Some domestic resisters also agreed on this view.

Many of the coup resisters believe that how they participate in the resistance is more important than where they are located. For those abroad, maintaining a connection with the struggle and not forgetting the ground realities is essential.

One critique was that people holding key responsibilities in the resistance should remain on the ground, instead of residing abroad. There is concern that if many key resisters leave, the movement inside the country will weaken.

“The real resistance fighters are on the ground. If you're not physically living with those fighting, you can't fully understand their feelings about peace. Some things can't be heard with the ears. You must listen with the heart. To do that, you need to be close, heart to heart.”

- Interviewee No. I007, Domestic coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 38 years old, Launglong, Tanintharyi

“Domestic life” Vs. “Exile life”

And domestic coup resisters often perceived that people living overseas have more comfortable lives. Those abroad feel misunderstood regarding their difficulties abroad, such as not having proper work, legal status, and security. Social media further amplifies this divide. Pictures posted by those exiles showing outings and comfortable lifestyles reinforce domestic perceptions that these individuals are detached from the daily struggles.

There were also perceptions that some resisters have left for foreign countries due to dreams of living in third countries with refugee status.

Information and Communications

Differences in access to information, lived experiences, and day-to-day realities often lead to disagreements. A key concern is the lack of open and mutual communication. There is a general perception that information sharing and communication between domestic and exile resisters is insufficient to improve mutual understanding.

This group-based mindset (Us Vs Them mindset) can also influence political opinions.

“This kind of division and blame-shifting only delays the revolution and increases the suffering. Our usual approach is weak on unity toward a solution. Pointing fingers at each other won’t change anything. What we should ask is, ‘How can each person contribute from where they are?’ ”

- Interviewee No. I002-25, Exile coup resister, Male, Agnostic, 34 years old, Dawei-Tanintharyi

4.2 Impact on future peacebuilding efforts

The majority of participants believed that most people who leave abroad will get more chances to gain open perspectives, diverse work experience, and further educational experiences. These experiences are seen as potentially beneficial for the country’s future reconstruction and peacebuilding efforts.

“Ideally, the split between domestic and overseas efforts should be strategic. For example, some should be sent to study. But what we're seeing now isn’t systematic. People are just doing what they can, based on their circumstances.”

- Interviewee No. I021-25, Exile coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 45 years old, Dawei-Taninthari

However, if the divide is viewed solely through the lens of domestic ("On-Ground") versus exiles ("On-Air"), it can lead to increased conflict and make trust-building more difficult.

After the revolution, different views were likely to emerge regarding those who stayed versus those who left. Some may accept the reasons people left, while others may hold resentments, perceiving that those abroad only returned after the struggle ended.

“There will be two classes. One will be the elite coup resister, and the other will be the on-ground coup resister. Imagine the 15th anniversary of the revolution. A political elite who lived in Chiang Mai will deliver a keynote about how they resisted, while someone who spent the entire time as an on-ground coup resister

will sit quietly in the corner. Our society will always have these two social classes.”

- Interviewee No. I001-25, Exile coup resister, Buddhist, Male, 32 years old, Yaybhyu, Tanintharyi

It is a summary of finding 2. Please see **Table 8** below.

Table 8: Summary of Finding 4
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Research question no.	Finding
<p>4.1</p> <p>Social and psychological dynamics among the coup resisters</p>	<p>Divisions have existed between domestic and exile coup resisters.</p> <p>Domestic coup resisters’ views</p> <p>Exile coup resisters left for more comfortable lives. They lack understanding of on-the-ground realities and sometimes express overly bold opinions.</p> <p>Most domestic resisters believe that real resistance must be grounded.</p> <p>Exile coup resisters’ views</p> <p>Domestic coup resisters misunderstand the difficulties of exile and migrant life.</p> <p>Many exile coup resisters believe they can better support the resistance once in a safer location, according to their skills.</p> <p>Most common view</p> <p>How they participate in the resistance is more important than where they are located. Maintaining a connection with the struggle and not forgetting the ground realities is essential.</p> <p>Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Differences in access to information and knowing realities. (2) Lack of open and mutual communication. (3) Social media: Pictures posted by those exiles show outings and comfortable lifestyles.
<p>4.2</p> <p>Impact on future peacebuilding efforts</p>	<p>Division can lead to increased conflict and make trust-building more difficult. Many resisters hope that exile experiences, such as work and education, are seen as potentially beneficial for the country’s future reconstruction and peacebuilding efforts.</p>

SUMMARY

The following is a summary of the influencing factors and decision-making processes of coup resisters, based on the different decisions they made

Finding 1 for RQ1:

The majority of the coup resisters are young and stay abroad. Life was generally filled with peace, freedom, hope, and the rule of law. All sectors were negatively affected by the military coup and declined.

Finding 2 for RQ2:

Coup resisters perceived the military as inhumane, religious extremists, and a self-serving institution. There is no disagreement among coup resisters regarding the value of the resistance. However, they are concerned when some individuals or groups become authoritarian and act similarly to a junta.

Coup resisters were motivated by the desire to reclaim democracy, freedom, justice, and moral obligation to be involved in the movement.

Personal values or beliefs did not primarily influence the decisions of exile coup resisters, while external factors were the most influential to flee. In contrast, domestic coup resisters strongly stand on their family values and belief in the revolution.

Finding 3 for RQ3:

Although both domestic and exile coup resisters faced similar security concerns, their responses and decisions differed. Among exile coup resister, security was the most influential factor in their decision. Domestic coup resisters also faced similar pressure. However, they decided to remain for their deep value in family life and their physical participation in the movement.

Finding 4 for RQ4:

Division can lead to increased conflict and make trust-building more difficult for the country's future reconstruction and peacebuilding efforts.

DISCUSSION

As previously discussed, the psychological and external factors influenced the resisters differently, with domestic actors often driven by values and commitment, and exiles responding primarily to external pressures such as safety and opportunity.

However, this section will discuss the role of cognitive capacity and creating personal narratives.

Cognitive Capacity

Many of them stated that they were not particularly aware of these internal psychological influences and their interaction with external factors. Decision-Making Theory (Simon, 1947), particularly its emphasis on bounded rationality, reflects that limited time, information, and cognitive capacities can affect decision-making.

These findings gave rise to the following questions:

(1) Cognitive Capacity and Climate of Fear

What is the relation between cognitive capacity and climate of fear?

Did a lack of awareness of psychological factors and their interactions occur because of limited cognitive capacity, or the climate of fear led to extreme stress and uncertainty, or both? Can the climate of fear also impact cognitive capacity positively?

(2) Cognitive Capacity and Sense of Urgency

Due to security concerns, many of the resisters leave the country with a sense of urgency, more or less. So, what is the role of a sense of urgency in cognitive capacity? Can a sense of emergency also impact cognitive capacity positively?

Holding beliefs and creating personal narratives

Differences in perceptions and attitudes between those resisting from within the country and those from abroad reflect what is described in Motivated Reasoning (Ziva Kunda, 1990) and Cognitive Dissonance Theory (Leon Festinger, 1957). Individuals hold onto positions that align with their self-interest or established beliefs.

Notably, while domestic resisters claim that they understand their counterparts abroad, they tend to hold the belief that resistance is more effective on the ground. Similarly, exile resisters emphasize that the way they participate is more important than where they participate from.

Implications for resistance and peacebuilding

Understanding the psychological dynamics behind individuals' decisions, as well as the social dynamics developing or potentially emerging among coup resisters, is crucial for both individual actors and resistance groups. Only deep insight and strategic engagement can strengthen the current resistance efforts and help future peacebuilding processes proceed with fewer obstacles.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the psychological and external social factors that influenced the coup resisters' decision to join the anti-coup movement and either stay in the country or flee abroad. It focused on the Tanintharyi region in Southern Myanmar. The findings indicated that both domestic and exile coup resisters are strongly motivated to oppose the military junta and to restore democracy, freedom, and justice. A sense of moral obligation also played a significant role in the decision-making process. However, the motivations and decision outcomes differed based on social status, community context, perceived security risks, and individual values and beliefs. Domestic coup resisters were primarily driven by internal psychological factors, including personal beliefs, values, and a sense of moral obligation, whereas exile coup resisters were influenced by external factors, such as concerns for their own and their families' safety, experiences of repression, and access to opportunities. These differences reflected deeper psychological and social dynamics within the resistance movement, which need to be recognized and addressed to strengthen unity and collaboration in the long term of the anti-coup movement and to guide future peacebuilding strategies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- (1) The coup resisters should recognize that individuals have different rationalities and the right to make personal choices regarding how they participate in the movement.
- (2) The individuals and organizations should strengthen the recognition of mutual roles and interdependence between domestic and exile coup resisters.
- (3) In-person meetings should be strategically organized instead of online meetings to improve communication and mutual respect among resisters.

- (4) Movement leaders should develop strategic approaches to determine whether to be domestic or exile coup resisters for the long-term movement and future peacebuilding and nation-building efforts.
- (5) Psychological education on rationality, decision-making, and cognitive awareness should be integrated into the movement.

APPENDIX

Appendix A: Index of Item Objectives Concurrence (IOC)

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Number	Research Question	Questions for informal conversation
RQ 1	What is the profile of coup resisters?	RQ 1.1 Can you tell me about your background (e.g., Age, Gender, Religion, Township, Current residence, education, profession, experience in activism)? RQ 1.2 What was your life like before the coup? RQ 1.3 How has the coup affected your life, family, friends, and community?
RQ 2	What psychological factors influence the decision of coup resisters to leave or stay in Tanintharyi?	RQ 2.1 How would you describe your perception toward the Military Junta? RQ 2.2 How would you describe your perception toward the resistance movement? RQ 2.3 What do your psychological factors (Attitudes, Personal Values, Beliefs, etc) motivate you to resist the coup by the military junta? RQ 2.4 What do your psychological factors (Attitudes, Personal Values, Beliefs, etc) motivate you to leave or stay in the country after the coup?
RQ 3	What external factors (security, family, friends, community, media/social media, personal experience, etc.) influence the decision of coup resisters to leave or stay in Tanintharyi, and	RQ 3.1 What external factors (security, family, friends, community, media/social media, personal experience, etc.) do influence your decision-making process to stay or leave the Tanintharyi, and how? RQ 3.2

	how psychological factors interact with them?	How do your personal beliefs, values, and attitude interact with the external factors in the decision-making process to stay or leave?
RQ 4	How do anti-coup defenders perceive the consequences of their decisions on the unity and direction of the resistance?	<p>RQ 4.1 Have you noticed any psychological and social dynamics within the resistance movement regarding staying or leaving the Tanintharyi?</p> <p>RQ 4.2 How do you perceive your decision will impact the resistance movement and future peacebuilding efforts in Myanmar?</p>

Appendix B: The List of Coup Resisters' Profiles
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No.	Gender	Age	Title	University Education	Home Town	Current Place	Religion
I001-25	Male	32	Digital Officer	Graduated	Yaybhyu, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I002-25	Male	34	Social Worker	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Agnostic
I003-25	Male	24	Journalist	3 rd Year-Engineering	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Atheist
I004-25	Male	41	Chief Reporter	High School	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Ranaung, Thailand	Buddhist
I005-25	Male	26	Journalist	Graduated	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Atheist
I006-25	Female	30	Accountant	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Bangkok, Thailand	Buddhist
I007-25	Male	38	Journalist	3 rd Year-History	LaungLone, Tanintharyi	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Buddhist
I008-25	Male	58	Professor	Post-Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Buddhist

I009-26	Male	64	Political Activist	2 nd Year-Philosophy	Kyunt Su, Tanintharyi	Hua Hin, Thailand	Buddhist
I010-25	Female	31	Social Worker	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I011-25	Male	24	Graphic Designer	2 nd year-Law	Yayphyu, Tanintharyi	Yangon, Myanmar	Buddhist
I012-25	Male	26	Barista	Graduated	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Bangkok, Thailand	Buddhist
I013-25	Male	25	Social Worker	5 th Year-Engineering	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I014-25	Male	35	General Worker	High School	Yayphyu, Tanintharyi	Suratharni, Thailand	Buddhist
I015-25	Female	25	Graphic Designer	4 th Year-Engineering	Yayphyu, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I016-25	Female	26	Student	Post-Graduated	Tayetchaung, Tanintharyi	Bangkok, Thailand	Buddhist
I017-25	Male	29	Finance Officer	Graduated	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I018-25	Male	35	Social Worker	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I019-25	Female	22	Presenter	1 st Year-Engineering	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I020-25	Female	25	Journalist	Graduated	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Chiang Mai, Thailand	Buddhist
I021-25	Male	45	Digital Editor	Post-Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Maesot, Thailand	Buddhist

I022-25	Male	28	Teacher	4 th Year-Myanmar , Dip-Ed	Myeik, Tanintharyi	Myeik, Thailand	Atheist
I023-25	Male	32	Rebel	Graduated	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Dawei, Tanintharyi	Atheist
I024-25	Male	37	Journalist	High School	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Launglone, Tanintharyi	Buddhist

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The Role of the Catholic Church in Peacebuilding During the Three-Year Post-Coup Period in Myanmar

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ABSTRACT

Myanmar is in a post-coup era, partly governed by a military junta (the military council also known as the Tatmadaw). The conflict has been both intricate and multifaceted. The Catholic Church has played a notable peacebuilding role, but its stance since the coup has faced scrutiny. This study uses desk-based research with online monitoring, analyzing relevant news sources and websites. It employed a qualitative approach, incorporating both primary and secondary data, processed through framework analysis. The study identifies three key roles of the Catholic Church in peacebuilding during the three-year post-coup period: (1) social critic and prophet, (2) advocate for nonviolence and peace, and (3) provider of safe havens. From the military coup on February 1, 2021, to January 2024, the Catholic Church in Myanmar consistently upheld nonviolence and peacebuilding. Overall, it neither endorsed nor supported both the violent military rule and the violent resistance movement.

Keywords: Catholic Church, Coup, Myanmar, Nonviolence, Peacebuilding

Introduction

Background and Context

The 2021 coup d'état was staged by the Myanmar military (also known as the Tatmadaw) led by Senior General Min Aung Hlaing of the Armed Forces in the early morning of February 1, 2021. The coup then leaders declared that the results of the November 2020 general election were invalid and imposed a state of emergency for one year, which was later extended every six months. This was more than an attempt against the elected civilian government. Concurrently, the military arrested State Counsellor Aung San Suu Kyi and other senior officials of the National League for Democracy (NLD) party on the grounds of widespread fraud in the last general election, and they have continued to detain them. However, the military takeover caused nationwide protests, with hundreds of thousands of people taking to the streets. Peaceful demonstrations were common tactics of the mass movement by the protestors, and they were met with a series of brutal crackdowns by the military. Within the first five months of the coup, the deadly actions of Myanmar state security forces resulted in nearly nine hundred people being killed and more than six thousand people being arrested. This included the arrest of elected representatives, civilian officials, protest leaders, and journalists, as well as the use of live ammunition against unarmed protesters. The consequences of the military's attacks, militarization through its various institutions and vast suppression over the people who protested its acts and political oppositions, mobilized broad civil disobedience and guerrilla-style armed resistance. This led to a new kind of civil war. Today, the civil disobedience movement includes defections from military or civil service resulting in neutralized individuals or freedom fighters, and the resistance movement has organized people's defense forces and local militias against the Myanmar military and its subordinates. Consequently, the escalation of violence has forced hundreds of thousands of people to flee their homes. The social and economic situations in the country have been deteriorating, and even insecurity for individuals and families have continued to rise. Although the military junta's claim that the coup was legal under the 2008 constitution, outcasted opposition parties (especially the NLD), non-state armed revolutionaries, and international democratic community (such as US, UK, EU, and Australia) rejected its claim and contended its illegal and illegitimate status. Since then, the country's political dynamics have changed and have led to a destructive situation in general (Baik, 2021; Clare, 2021; Mahtani, 2021; Prashad, 2021). According to Adiningtyas Dwiputri Samsuerizal, E. R. Hidayat, and Achmed Sukendro (2021), the military coup has dashed hopes for democracy in Myanmar. However, for some people, it

may create different opportunities on the tradition of conflict per se as conflict system has changed to some extent.

Thoughts before the Military Coup D'état

Many people hoped that political changes and reforms between 2011 and 2020, along with a series of peace talks and reconciliations with various ethnic revolutionary organizations, however, would provide better opportunities for the political, social, economic, educational, and health sectors. Likewise, (Ganesan, 2017) found that the democratization process had structurally and institutionally strengthened the peace process. On the other hand, the new Thein Sein-led military-civilian-hybrid government included a congenial working relationship with political opposition groups and individuals (Ganesan, 2013) since the first part of Myanmar's transition to democracy.

The military could still control the power of the state partly as it retained a de facto veto over future constitutional changes by reserving a quarter of the seats in both houses of Hluttaw [parliament] for military appointees. It was ambiguous and even unexpected for many people, including the ruling NLD party and other political organizations, that the coup would be staged. However, it was aware that the military regime will continue to hold control over the country (Szu-Tu & Ku, 2017).

Actors of Peace and Conflict

Different countries have different and similar concerns on Myanmar's situation. International actors for peace and conflict in Myanmar can be defined as ASEAN member countries, the US, the UK, Australia, EU member countries, Japan, and China based on their overt responses or relations with Myanmar and its conflicting parties. Apparently, internal actors may include the military junta and its militias and administrative units, Ethnic Revolutionary Organizations (EROs), newly formed resistance groups (PDFs - People's Defense Forces and PABs - People Administrative Bodies), political oppositions (NLD - National League for Democracy, CRPH - Committee Representing Pyidaungsu Hluttaw, NUG - National Unity Government, and NUCC - National Unity Consultative Council), student and youth groups, general strike committees, religious actors, and other political parties. However, not all actors or groups in each category may be actively resisting the military junta under the circumstances, as different actors may have different interests and stances.

Among them, the role of religious actors cannot be separated from any peace and conflict, whether theoretically or practically. As understood, religions play a role in both inner peace and outer peace for individuals and societies. However, this does not mean a religion can

be a source of conflict. Religion, in nature, cannot be seen as a source of violence; only some bad practitioners can be held accountable (Kalm, 2004).

Especially, in order to deal with conflict, different religions may have different or similar roles and may possess different backgrounds and experiences for the sake of peacebuilding at levels from the micro-level to the meta-level (Galtung & Fischer, 2013).

Peace, Religious Actors, and the Study

A study focusing on the role of a particular religion in a specific context may and should be an option or a choice. The role of religious actors around the world can obviously be studied, and this kind of studies, including that of the Catholic Church, may be abundant for learners and for further research. For instance, in history, the Catholic Church has played an important or influential role in the context of peace and conflict in different countries such as Western countries, Latin America countries, the Philippines, and Africa too (Appleby, 2000). However, the Catholic Church in some countries may not be well studied in terms of peace and conflict, although it may have a well and active role in positively contributing to particular countries or societies. According to an abstract of a journal article by Simonia Aida Alekseevna in 2015 [the author's name was translated from Russian to English by using Google Translate on 25 October 2023, but the abstract is originally written in English], up to the year 2015, there were only 770,000 Catholics in Myanmar, and the topic about the Roman Catholic Church in Myanmar was poorly researched, although the Roman Catholic Church was brought to this country by Portuguese sailors since 1511.

Catholic Church has played an overt role by oftentimes calling for peacebuilding in Myanmar and expressing its concerns about violence escalation and negative consequences. Even since this military coup, a nonviolent solution to Myanmar's conflict, as well as dialogue and reconciliation between conflicting parties, were cited in the calls by Pope Francis and Myanmar Cardinal Charles Maung Bo, hereafter referred to as Cardinal CMB (Bo, 2021a, 2021b; RFA Burmese, 2021, 2023). On the other hand, Cardinal CMB was criticized and condemned on social media because he celebrated Christmas together with the leader of the military junta in the Christmas season (BBC Burmese, 2022).

Research Problem

Studies about religions around the world, including the Catholic Church, are abundant. There are various and numerous studies about Buddhism in Myanmar too. However, this study about the role of the Catholic Church in particular country (Myanmar, formerly Burma) and certain period (since the 2021 coup), as well as especially its role in peacebuilding, was rarely

researched, according to the Simonia Aida Alekseevna in 2015, and it is a niche which would fill a gap in this peace academia.

Additionally, it may give a clue to solving a real problem, if there is a general public's misunderstanding of the role of the Catholic Church in the area of peace and conflict in Myanmar.

Research Purpose

The purpose of my research was to explore the role of the Catholic Church in peacebuilding during the three-year post-coup period in Myanmar, from February 2021 to January 2024.

Research Question

What is the role of the Catholic Church in peacebuilding during the three-year post-coup period in Myanmar, from February 2021 to January 2024?

Research Objective

To explore the role of the Catholic Church in peacebuilding during the three-year post-coup period in Myanmar through a study of the Catholic Church in Myanmar using an identified theoretical framework and by validating the argument stated in the significance of the research.

Significance of the Research

It was intended to fill a gap at the intersection of the role of Catholic Church, religious peacebuilding, and the Myanmar context in the interim since the military coup staged on February 1, 2021, especially between February 2021 and January 2024. Moreover, it was an observation of a non-Catholic native citizen of Myanmar, and a different perspective would be presented. Additionally, sources such as news, letters, and messages written in the Myanmar (Burmese) language have been fairly applied; therefore, this desk-based research is more significant not only with its unique perspective but also with local vernacular rather than reflecting other countries' languages and their perspectives or Western media voices.

Myanmar's post-coup era is already over three years, and it may be prolonged beyond this point. However, a study of a three-year period is sufficient to understand the role of Catholic Church in Myanmar, and it can capture immediate impacts and provide insights into long-term strategies of the study and the Church's role in peacebuilding in reality. Therefore, it can give timely comparative analysis against other studies, as well as can offer valuable information for readers or practitioners in the field of peacebuilding towards policy implications. Without a limitation of timeframe, there may lead to no direction and may not

support to a long-term study. Research on the role of Catholic Church in Myanmar for the sake of peace should be set with a boundary, and further research will surely come in the future. At least, this study will pave the way for all readers to gain new knowledge through a specified lens.

However, within my research question and research objective, I have made this argument the central aspect of the study: since the military coup on February 1, 2021, over the three years from February 2021 to January 2024, the Catholic Church in Myanmar stood for nonviolence and peacebuilding. This implies, as a whole, that it neither endorsed nor supported both the violent military rule and the violent resistance movement.

Literature Review

Religious Peacebuilding

In this section, the most relevant knowledge to this study from various literature is presented after a review, ranging from nonviolence philosophy to the uniqueness of religious peacebuilding.

General Nonviolence Philosophy

In the notion of religious peacebuilding, which is nonviolent per se (Appleby, 2000, p. 13), life must be preserved through nonviolent confrontations and what the Quakers call “bearing witness.” We must obstruct a wrong without offering personal violence to its perpetrators, as stated by Greenpeace (Ryan, 2002, p. 6). A Quaker is a member of the Society of Friends (or Friends Church), a Christian group that stresses the guidance of the Holy Spirit, rejects outward rites and an ordained ministry, and has a long tradition of actively working for peace and opposing war (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2023).

In like manner, a prominent scholar of global religion and peace, R. Scott Appleby, described the basis for peace using Mahatma Gandhi's idea that "every major moral and religious tradition has long emphasized the ideals of truth and nonviolence as the foundation for authentic and lasting peace" (Appleby, 2000, p. 141). On the other hand, Gandhi once said, "...but I believe that nonviolence is infinitely superior to violence" (Appleby, 2000, p. 12). For the sake of peace and peacebuilding, religion should be nonviolent, since religious violence poses a significant threat to religious peacebuilding and its peacebuilders (Appleby, 2000, p. 8).

From Peacebuilding to Religious Peacebuilding

Peacebuilding covers many processes and activities involved in resolving violent

conflicts and establishing sustainable peace. Such activities might include, for example, dialogue, reconciliation, restorative justice, trauma healing, policy reform, or peace leadership training. It is also an umbrella term for actions that bring people together and address a conflict's underlying structural causes, as well as post-conflict action (Garred & Abu-Nimer, 2018, p. 6). In a broader sense, faith-based peacebuilding, as faith makes peacebuilding religious, refers to an interactive peacebuilding process in which one or more parties are motivated or influenced by religious identity or experience. To understand the influence of religion in peacebuilding, it is necessary to be open to considering all forms of religion in peacebuilding (Garred & Abu-Nimer, 2018, p. 7).

Briefly, religion is the human response to a reality perceived as sacred. At this point, it is sufficed to say that religion, as an interpreter of the sacred, discloses and celebrates the transcendent source and significance of human existence. Commonly defined, religion embraces a creed, a cult, a code of conduct, and a confessional community. Thus, religion constitutes an integral culture capable of forming personal and social identity, influencing subsequent experience and behavior in profound ways (Appleby, 2000, pp. 8–9). Using a term of Appleby "militant", its role is crucial, particularly that of the religious militant. Religious people are those who hold leadership roles in their communities and take action in the pursuit of justice and the building of peaceful communities. However, for Appleby, religious militants are willing to risk their lives and livelihood for reconciliation and service to the poor and oppressed (Appleby, 2000, p. x). On the negative side, a religious militant can also be an extremist, far beyond the role of peacemaker. To possess tolerance, which is an important religious value, and for the sake of peace, nonviolent religious militants are most favorable. Therefore, nonviolent religious militants are religious and militant peacemakers, encouraging peacemaking and reconciliation (Appleby, 2000, pp. 6–21).

Overall, in religious peacebuilding, religion has a significant influence. Religious leaders play an indisputably important role, and religious peacebuilding is vital for peace (Garred & Abu-Nimer, 2018, pp. 6–8).

Uniqueness of Religious Peacebuilding

On their spiritual identity, religious peacebuilders' approaches to addressing conflict may include a strong emphasis on scriptures, symbols, rituals, and prayer or meditation. Then, they insist on pursuing positive peace with an emphasis on personal transformative change. These faith-based peacebuilders are rarely satisfied with negative peace because they are pursuing a much more expansive peace vision (in different languages: shanti; salaam; shalom,

etc.). After that, these faith-based practitioners have unique access to the sacred in their own communities. Their natural capacity to enter mosques, churches, synagogues, temples, or ancestral holy grounds provides a powerful window or gate into the inner dynamics of faith communities – an entry point that secular peacebuilders cannot easily gain. If religious identity is a powerful motivator and is trustworthy within the respective religious institutions, these religious peacebuilders can take up insider roles. As recognized by coreligionists, they can play as agents of change (Garred & Abu-Nimer, 2018, p. 9).

Religious peacebuilding ranges from religion's compassionate side to charitable endeavors and humanitarian relief work. It encompasses appreciation of religion and religious actors for their effectiveness, readiness, and utilization of religious tradition and its sources for positive peace, such as sacred scriptures and/or codified oral teachings and commentaries. Two-thirds of contemporary wars turn on issues of religious, ethnic, or national identity, and the role of local religious leaders becomes more important. Their contributions include resolving the immediate crisis as well as reforming the long-term social conditions that fostered and perpetuated the religious hatred or racism at the root of the conflict (Appleby, 2000, pp. 16–18).

A Theoretical Framework of Religious Peacebuilding and the Role of Religious Peacebuilders

Religious peacebuilding can be carried out by religious institutions, organizations, or individuals. However, religious peacebuilding in this context is, as a whole, about conflict transformation on the ground and post-conflict structural reform (a peacebuilding process that constitutes the third dimension of religious conflict transformation, see Figure 1) and also includes the efforts of people working remotely from actual sites of deadly conflict. For religious peacebuilding scholars, it is not necessarily important to be in the face of conflict. The roles of religious peacebuilder can include legal advocates of religious human rights, scholars conducting research on cross-cultural and interreligious dialogue, and theologians and ethicists who are probing and strengthening their religious communities' traditions of nonviolent militance. According to Appleby (2000, pp. 211–212), there are three dimensions of religious conflict transformation: conflict management (CM), conflict resolution (CR), and structural reform. Within each dimension, religious actors may participate in conflict transformation under three different sets of sociopolitical circumstances, such as the crisis mode, the saturation mode, and the intervention mode. Religious peacebuilders work together across different groups or forces. Indeed, “religious peacebuilding” is a misnomer if it leads

one to believe that religious actors can transform dimensions of modern conflict by functioning independently of government and other secular and religious actors. Moreover, religious peacebuilders can work together in their particular roles in different forms as non-state (N/S) actors, “around the world, this informal and unofficial alliance has been a powerful force for social change” (Appleby, 2000, p. 215).

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of Religious Peacebuilding and the Role of Religious Peacebuilders. It was figured by the Author in 2023 based on the book section of Religion and Conflict Transformation by R. Scott Appleby (2000)

The roles of religious peacebuilders can be identified for each phase, with several roles or functions depending on their contributions to religious peacebuilding, also known as religious conflict transformation. In the phase of conflict management, their roles may include serving as social critics, prophets for early warning, advocates, and/or providers of safe havens for refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs). In conflict resolution, they may act as mediators (either as outsider-neutral or insider-partial mediators) in negotiations, as event monitors, as facilitators in talks, and/or in another unspecified role. In post-conflict peacebuilding (which is structural reform), their role may generally be as contributors to long-term sociopolitical reform and as providers of security and justice as non-state (N/S) actors. In this phase, they may assume roles similar to those in conflict management and conflict resolution, such as social critics, prophets, humanitarian relief providers, or advocates for the

poor and defenseless. However, there are three modes of participation. Crisis mode is mostly related to conflict management and conflict resolution; it is short term and these peacebuilders need to work full time. In crisis mode, the conflict situation is intense and largely unanticipated, and usually religious organizations are not well-prepared. However, they may be actively involved in the social dynamics of political change without sufficient capability to respond to conflict, unlike in saturation mode. Based on the Northern Ireland experience, saturation mode is defined as the best chance for evolving into actual religious peacebuilding in transforming conflict. It can be a long-term process, and peacebuilders are required to work full time. Under this mode, internal mediation among conflicting parties may occur. Saturation mode may have conditions similar to those of crisis mode, such as a spontaneous, diffuse, and unstructured series of reactions to the threats; however, institutions and organizations, with their commitments, will be able to respond well. Last but not least, the interventionist mode for mediators and magisters especially provides a chance for external actors. In this mode, peacebuilders may or may not work on a short-term or long-term basis, and either part-time or full-time. The role of external actors is largely needed, ranging from conflict management to conflict transformation, to sustain the momentum of peacebuilding. It represents the next level following saturation mode. However, external religious actors work in collaboration with religious parties and institutions on the ground, whether their religions or traditions are different or the same (Appleby, 2000).

Moreover, according to Little and Appleby (2004) and Appleby (2000), while the role of religious peacebuilders includes that of social critics, they are also peacekeepers who physically and morally discourage violence. Furthermore, they tend to support the making of peace agreements. They can also play a facilitator and mediator role in negotiations for conflict resolution. Additionally, as part of conflict transformation, they always advocate nonviolence and reconciliation among conflicting parties.

Methodology

Methods, Scope, and Limitation of the Study

The study employed a qualitative approach, utilizing desk-based research, including online monitoring, without the involvement of human subjects. The integration of various data sources and platforms for data collection supplemented this desk research by providing real-time insights and critical perspectives.

This study was my initial exploration which gave attention to the role of the Catholic

Church in post-coup Myanmar, specifically examining what it was and what it was not. The study focused on the general nature and dynamics of action in terms of its role (Francis, 2007, pp. 39–40) rather than individuals' inner feelings or entities' specific behaviors and interactions. However, as the main figure representing the Catholic Church in Myanmar, Cardinal Charles Maung Bo played the most important role in this study. The study covered the period from February 2021 to January 2024. Both secondary and primary data were utilized, sourced from news reports, news articles, letters and statements, and existing literature. Data were gathered from various platforms, including credible online news media and social media websites. However, the availability of data was limited by my access to online resources.

Ethics, Interpretation, and Validity

A clear understanding of the context was first established through general observation. The research topic was then in depth through a comprehensive review of the literature and progressive monitoring of existing information and updates. Throughout this study, I strived to maintain impartiality and ensure the research remained fact-based. Only publicly available sources were used, eliminating concerns regarding confidentiality. Proper citations and references were carefully applied to prevent plagiarism. This research underwent a degree of validation through both the research proposal presentation and the final research presentation in late 2023, with the participation of select members of the academic community in which I am engaged.

Data Collection and Analysis

For data collection, various sources and numerous items were utilized including reliable online news media and websites such as RFA Burmese and BBC Burmese. Specifically, for Catholic monitoring sources, three out of nine websites were largely explored and monitored in line with the purpose of this research, as words from Catholic Church leaders have been commonly disseminated through these social media. These sources include CBCM OSC (Catholic Bishops' Conference of Myanmar - Office of Social Communication), RVA Myanmar (Radio Veritas Asia Myanmar), and KYESE Myanmar - ကြေးစည်မြန်မာ. The reliability of the data sources was verified through consultations with two active Catholic members in Myanmar. While they did not serve as research participants for the study's findings, their insights were valuable in gaining a general understanding of the Catholic Church's nature

in Myanmar.

Data analysis was conducted manually and flexibly using framework analysis, progressing from familiarization and thematic framework identification to reviewing data extracts, summarizing findings, and displaying data in accordance with the theoretical framework applied in this research. Data were systematically compared and contrast, then interpreted based on my conscientiousness and rationality by considering patterns, correlation, and causality (Ritchie & Spencer, 1994).

Findings and Discussion

Findings were obtained through the lens of the theoretical framework on the role of the Catholic Church in post-coup Myanmar from February 2021 to January 2024, using framework analysis as the data analysis method. Therefore, the major findings are presented in three categories and discussed simultaneously as follows. However, while there may be more than three roles of the Catholic Church in this context, these categories have been appropriately organized for the purposes of this research.

(1) Social Critic and Prophet

The findings indicate that the Catholic Church has played a role as both a social critic and a prophet. Pope Francis, in his statement on October 20, 2023, calling for fasting and prayer for peace, asserted that war cannot solve problems; instead, it causes devastation, incites hatred, and destroys the future (Bo, 2023). Similarly, Cardinal Charles Maung Bo (CMB) addressed the people, civilian leaders, the Tatmadaw (Myanmar military), and the international community on February 3, 2021, stating that the country was in darkness and facing the greatest challenge in its history (Bo, 2021a, p. 1). This aligns with Appleby's (2000, p. 213) argument that religious leaders, as social critics, call government officials and political, military, and business elites to account for unjust and abusive politics. However, the Church's explicit call for justice remains less evident. As a prophetic voice, religious leaders can serve as early warners of societal rifts and systemic human rights abuses that could escalate into greater violence (Appleby, 2000, p. 213).

This role is further exemplified in Cardinal CMB's statement, where he condemns the Tatmadaw's unilateral seizure of power, emphasizing that global leaders have condemned this act and will continue to do so. He further asserts that the people of Myanmar have grown weary of the Tatmadaw's promises and no longer trust its deceptive statements (Bo, 2021a, p. 3).

(2) Advocate for Nonviolence and Peace

As religious peacebuilders can play an advocacy role, Pope Francis urged people to avoid devastation and to heed the cries of children, the poor, and humanity for peace (Bo, 2023). Similarly, in his statement from February 2021, Cardinal Charles Maung Bo (CMB) called for an end to violence against the people of Myanmar (Bo, 2021a, p. 3).

Advocacy does not necessarily require a religious peacebuilder (whether as an individual or an organization) to be a legal advocate. In this context, they can act as human rights advocates and advocates of humanism as well. Accordingly to Appleby (2000, p. 215), the roles of a social critic and an advocate for the oppressed can be intertwined. For instance, in the 1986 national elections in the Philippines, Catholic social justice advocates also served as election monitors. It remains unknown how the Catholic Church in Myanmar engaged with the 2020 general elections. However, Catholic individuals or organizations can serve as social justice advocates, peace advocates, or monitors of political processes while representing the Church (Appleby, 2000, pp. 208, 236). Through the leadership of Cardinal CMB, the Catholic Church in Myanmar has consistently upheld nonviolence and dialogue as pathways to peace. He expressed concern over the military's nationwide crackdown on opposition forces and called for an end to violent actions, advocating instead for an inclusive dialogue involving all stakeholders (BBC Burmese, 2022).

Within its role as an advocate for nonviolence and peace, the Catholic Church has maintained a clear stance on dialogue, negotiation, and reconciliation. Additionally, its call for prayer for peace as a sacred practice has been a notable aspect of its advocacy efforts.

Dialogue, Negotiation, and Reconciliation

According to Cardinal CMB's message (Bo, 2021a, pp. 1, 3), finding a long-term and sustainable solution is necessary to overcome the "darkness" caused by the military coup. He questioned, "*Was there no sufficient dialogue or meeting between the elected civilian government and the Tatmadaw?*" and urged that all disputes be resolved through dialogue, emphasizing that there is always potential for peace.

John Paul Lederach (Appleby, 2000, p. 18) asserts that sustainable peace requires long-time antagonists not only to lay down their arms but also to work toward genuine reconciliation—socially defined relationships supported by a society-wide network of mechanisms that promote justice and address the root causes of enmity before they can regenerate destabilizing tensions. Consistent with this perspective, the Catholic Church in Myanmar has continuously called for dialogue, negotiation, and reconciliation. On December 23, 2021, *Tachileik News Agency* published a report titled, [unofficial translation] "Cardinal

CMB Specially Encourages Reconciliation Through Dialogue”(Tachileik News Agency, 2021a). Since December 2021, Cardinal CMB and his colleagues have faced public criticism for celebrating Christmas with the top leaders of the military junta. However, he maintained his stance, advocating for reconciliation and peace while emphasizing the need to seek solutions through dialogue rather than armed conflict (Bo, 2021b; Tachileik News Agency, 2021b). Eventually, on Christmas Eve, he met again with a high-ranking military general, the second-most senior leader of the junta, along with other Christian leaders. Despite the criticisms, he continued to advocate for peace and the well-being of the people (Myanmar Alinn Daily, 2023). Nonviolent religious militants are both religious peacemakers and militant peacemakers in their approach to conflict resolution (Appleby, 2000, p. 13). Therefore, if the Catholic Church has genuinely embraced religious peacebuilding, it is unsurprising that religious figures continue to encourage peacemaking and reconciliation.

A Sacred Practice: Prayer for Peace

Various websites affiliated with the Catholic Church in Myanmar have consistently posted daily prayers for peace and for the country. On October 20, 2023, Pope Francis also called on all Christians and others who desire peace to fast and pray. His statement included information about the increasing number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Gaza due to the Israel-Gaza war, reflecting the stance of nonviolent religious peacebuilders (Bo, 2023). Recently, a Catholic church in Mandalay hosted an interreligious prayer for peace in Myanmar and worldwide, which also served as a Christmas celebration. A post by RVA Myanmar on December 18, 2023, indicated that the event was attended not only by different Christian denominations and Buddhist monks and nuns but also by representatives from other religions. Peacebuilding often involves interreligious dialogue and activities rooted in religious communities' traditions of nonviolent militance. This aligns with their capacity to contribute meaningfully to peacebuilding (Appleby, 2000, p. 212).

Violent Behavior

In order to critically examine the context and conflict of this research, especially on the role of the Catholic Church, an exploration of the Church's violent behavior was also conducted. A case was rarely found. According to a Facebook page named "Independent Catholics for Justice Myanmar – ICJM," on November 22, 2023, it posted about a donation to the Chinland Defence Force CDF-Paletwa through ICJM from unnamed donors. The post also attached a “Certificate of Appreciation for Donation” given by the CDF-Paletwa, which is an armed organization and a People's Defense Force (ICJM, 2023a). This post reveals support for

a violent organization, and it can be inferred that some Catholics supported violent behavior. The purpose here is not to determine whether this behavior is justifiable or unjustifiable violence, but rather to explore whether the Church committed violence. To clarify, is this violent behavior an act of the Church, or does this Facebook page represent the Church? Furthermore, ICJM continued its support for armed groups, so called People's Defense Forces. For instance, posts about money donations through ICJM to different PDFs were made on December 29, 2023, January 3, 2024, and January 15, 2024, among others (ICJM, 2023c, 2024a, 2024b). ICJM also criticized Cardinal CMB's celebration of Christmas with a top leader of military junta, issuing an open letter on December 27, 2023 (ICJM, 2023b). However, a friend of mine, a young and active Catholic in Myanmar, explained to me on November 23, 2023, via Facebook Messenger that the Facebook page “Catholics for Justice Myanmar – ICJM” is managed by a Catholic priest personally, and its activities are minor. According to him, it does not represent the Catholic Church (Author, personal communication, November 23, 2023). Therefore, in this case, I have no reason to call the Catholic Church in Myanmar violent.

(3) Provider of Safe Havens

The third category of findings pertains to the role of the Catholic Church in Myanmar as a provider of safe havens during this interim period. According to a statement released on November 27, 2023 by the Loikaw Diocese, titled, "The Current Situation of Kayah State," the Diocese of Loikaw served as a provider of safe havens for conflict-affected internally displaced persons (IDPs). These individuals fled their residences due to the intensifying armed conflicts between the military junta and local resistance organizations, as well as the consequences of military junta airstrikes and shelling. On November 11, 2023, the compound of Christ the King in Kayah State accommodated an additional 800 IDPs, bringing the total number of displaced persons to over 1,300 (Shwe, 2023). However, this does not imply that both the safe havens and the IDPs were completely safe. After November 26, 2023, the bishop and the resident priests in the Diocese of Loikaw had to leave their Pastoral Center for another location due to the military intentionally fired the Pastoral Center with 120mm artillery.

According to Appleby (2000, p. 216), the concept of “safe havens” extended to the protection of victims of deadly conflict. This includes providing safe and healthy spaces, as well as witnessing the process of the safe return of IDPs and refugees. Religious leaders in Guatemala played a similar role in witnessing people's safe return to their homes from Mexico, people who had been expelled by the Guatemalan government.

Upon reflecting on this section, I have come to understand that religious peacebuilding is a form of religious conflict transformation, which has consistently applied tolerant and nonviolent means in addressing conflict. The distinct roles of religion are particularly prominent in specific conflict systems. Furthermore, anyone (whether an individual or organization) can be a religious peacebuilder if their work is aligned with religious traditions and uses religious resources to promote peace.

Conclusion

In summary, the demand of the Catholic Church in Myanmar since 2021 has ranged from conflict management and conflict resolution, which aim at peacekeeping and peacemaking respectively, to conflict transformation, which has looked beyond the conflict and has sought long-term peace. However, the role of Catholic Church in Myanmar has primarily remained active in Crisis Mode, and although it has frequently called for negotiation and reconciliation, there has been no tangible role in conflict resolution yet. The role of the Catholic Church in Myanmar in Saturation Mode remains unclear, and there is no evidence to suggest it is in this mode. However, it can be assumed that the intention and approach of the Catholic Church are fundamentally supportive of all phases of religious peacebuilding, particularly conflict transformation, as supported by Appleby's statement: "At the heart of peacebuilding is conflict transformation, the replacement of violent with nonviolent means of settling disputes" (Appleby, 2000, p. 212).

Additionally, the Catholic Church has frequently requested and offered prayers for peace through various means, including fasting prayers, in accordance with its religiosity (Bo, 2023).

The Catholic Church's position on nonviolence and its unique role in peacebuilding, as well as its calls for dialogue, negotiation, and reconciliation, have been overtly found without partiality to any of the conflicting parties.

Therefore, the argument that, since the military coup on February 1, 2021, the Catholic Church in Myanmar stood for nonviolence and peacebuilding remains valid. It appears that, as a whole, the Catholic Church neither endorsed nor supported the violent military rule nor the violent resistance movement.

Lastly, in terms of the role of Catholic Church in Myanmar on the internal political conflict, the rationale behind my argument is that there may be a misunderstanding by some about the role and the position of the Catholic Church. The thinking includes questions such as: Why does the Catholic Church in Myanmar not support the ongoing resistance movement,

and does the Church not want to stand for justice? Thereafter, a rhetorical question arises: If it is true that there is misunderstanding about the Catholic Church's role in Myanmar's internal political conflict, can their misunderstanding simply be a misunderstanding? Evidently, the Catholic Church would continue its position and the teachings it believes in, including encouraging dialogue, negotiation, and reconciliation, as well as practicing prayer for peace. Ultimately, the definition and position of justice made by the Catholic Church should be further study.

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Knowledge Regarding Pre-Birth, Conception Planning, and Childbirth Services in Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The high rate of maternal mortality in Zaria town highlights a pressing concern. The study aims to discover the knowledge of females on pre-birth, conception planning, and childbirth services. The aim of this paper is to discover the level of knowledge for women in access and use of these services in Zaria town. A content analysis method was utilized to know pre-birth, conception planning, and childbirth services use in the area. The findings reveal substantial gaps in knowledge, and cultural impacts affecting these service use. The study revealed women were generally knowledgeable about pre-birth care, childbirth and family planning services. Key barriers to family planning included spousal dissatisfaction and inclination for larger families. There is need for all-inclusive dissemination of precise information on conception planning to address cultural beliefs and false beliefs. Sensitization campaigns on conception planning services and the role of men in supporting these initiatives are crucial.

Keywords: Access, conception, culture, childbirth, peace education, pre-birth.

Introduction

Pre-birth care (PBC), conception planning (CP), and childbirth care represent essential pillars in the framework of protective health, significantly impacting the health outcomes of both mothers and their infants. These services encompass a wide array of interventions and support mechanisms aimed at safeguarding the health and well-being of women before, during, and after giving birth. Despite numerous global efforts and initiatives aimed at improving access to these vital services, a staggering number of individuals, particularly in underprivileged and rural areas, remain largely unaware of both their significance and the availability of such services in their communities. As defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), 2014), maternal health is not merely about the absence of disease rather, it encompasses a comprehensive approach to the well-being of women throughout the various stages of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. This holistic understanding highlights the integral role that maternal healthcare plays in ensuring both women's physical and mental health, ultimately leading to improved outcomes for their infants.

Adequate pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth care are fundamentally essential and protective, focusing on initial discovery of complications, therefore implementing necessary interventions that can significantly reduce maternal mortality rates, a crucial objective emphasized by sources such as Olugbenga-Bello, et al., (2011) and related statements from WHO and UNICEF (2010). While pregnancy is often viewed as a natural and physiological process, there exists a concerning pattern of underutilization of antenatal care services. This issue persists even among women who do not exhibit symptoms of illness or who may appear to be healthy. Various barriers compound this challenge, including socioeconomic factors, limited educational outreach, cultural beliefs, and inadequate access to healthcare facilities, which can hinder the ability of many women to seek and receive necessary care and peace education that can cater for their health before, during and after childbirth.

The overarching target of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services is to facilitate safe deliveries and promote the health of both mothers and infants. By ensuring that women receive comprehensive healthcare throughout their pregnancy journey, society can aid pave the way for healthier families, stronger communities, and a reduction in the rate of complications that often accompany childbirth. This approach not only improves individual outcomes but contributes to the broader objectives of public health and societal well-being. In essence, enhancing awareness and access to these critical services should be prioritized to empower

women and foster a healthier future for generations to come. The experience of motherhood is profoundly influenced by the availability and accessibility of maternal health services, which remain a pressing global concern. Significant disparities in the access to and utilization of these vital services can be observed around the world, particularly when comparing developed nations to those that are still developing. Such inequalities are shaped by a multitude of socioeconomic factors that include, but are not limited to, poverty levels, educational attainment, and geographical considerations. For instance, urban dwellers, particularly those with higher educational backgrounds, often enjoy enhanced access to comprehensive maternal health services compared to their rural counterparts, who may struggle with limited resources and lower levels of health education (Adewoye, et al., 2013).

This discrepancy is especially pronounced in Nigeria, where many women encounter formidable barriers that impede their ability to obtain essential maternal health care. Predominantly, these challenges stem from pervasive poverty and a significant lack of health literacy among the population. Research has shown that these socioeconomic hardships frequently hinder women from accessing necessary prenatal, delivery, and postnatal care, which are crucial for improving both maternal and child health outcomes (Fagbamigbe & Idemudia, 2016; Musa et al., 2013). The stakes are incredibly high, as the ability to receive adequate healthcare during and after pregnancy can mean the difference between life and death for both mothers and their newborns. In stark contrast, developed countries exhibit a markedly different landscape in terms of maternal health awareness and service utilization. In these nations, such as Australia, Canada, and Italy, there is a robust knowledge base regarding pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services. Numerous studies highlight the widespread awareness and frequent use of maternal healthcare facilities among women in these countries. For example, research conducted in Australia (Keleha, 2006) reveals a solid understanding of comprehensive health resources, while similar findings in Canada (Kolahdooz, et al., 2016) and Italy (Lauria et al., 2013) underscore the effectiveness of public health initiatives in promoting pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth health. This remarkable level of awareness and access stands in sharp contrast to the experiences faced by females in developing regions, calling attention to the urgent need for targeted interventions to bridge these gaps and ensure that all mothers, regardless of their circumstances, have the opportunity to receive the essential health services they require.

Similarly, research conducted in Uganda (Ssenooba et al., 2003) and Tunisia reveals that women in these regions are generally well-informed about the various services that pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth health facilities offer. They possess a substantial understanding of the resources available to assist them during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. In contrast, the situation is markedly different in South Africa, where women hailing from lower socioeconomic backgrounds frequently have limited awareness of the pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services that are accessible to them (Phillips, 2003). This lack of knowledge not only affects their ability to seek necessary medical care but may also directly impact their health outcomes and the health of their babies. In a notable divergence, women in Cameroon who belong to higher socioeconomic strata demonstrate a greater awareness of available maternal healthcare services, indicating a correlation between economic status and knowledge of health resources (McTavish & Moore, 2015). However, it is essential to highlight that economic standing is not the sole determining factor influencing women's awareness of maternal health services. Various other elements play a significant role in shaping this knowledge, including cultural beliefs, religious affiliations, and levels of educational attainment. For instance, women from more educated backgrounds may be more likely to engage with healthcare systems and consequently become more informed about the services available to them.

Furthermore, in Nigeria, stark disparities are evident regarding knowledge of antenatal, family planning, and childbirth services, especially when comparing the northern and southern regions of the country. The findings from the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS, 2014) illustrate this divide, indicating that women residing in the southern part of Nigeria generally possess a heightened awareness of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services in comparison to their northern counterparts. In many northern areas, women often recognize only basic maternal health services, which could severely limit their access to comprehensive care during critical periods such as pregnancy and childbirth. This lack of awareness creates barriers to the utilization of necessary health services, ultimately resulting in poorer pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth care (Onasoga, 2014) in these regions. Socio-economic factors such as education and access to information play a significant role in these inequalities (Butawa et al., 2010; Nuhu, 2010). For example, females with higher education levels are more likely to seek health services independently, while those with lower education often rely on

spousal approval (Hyacinth et al., 2006). The role of spousal approval determines the outcome of the service a woman can use.

Health knowledge is a critical determinant of women's ability to access appropriate health services and exercise her privileges (Zhao et al., 2009). Studies in Uganda and other developing countries have shown that women with higher education and occupation levels are more likely to be aware of and use health services (Nanlwanga, 2004; Levine et al., 2001). Education remains a key factor in improving knowledge of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services, as it enhances awareness and ability to access health information relevant for their health needs. Discriminatory and cultural practices and beliefs also affects knowledge of women on health services, a need for targeted interventions to address these disparities. Interventions focusing on community-based education and male involvement have a means of improving knowledge on antenatal, family planning and childbirth services in low-resource settings (World Bank, 2021; UNICEF, 2022). Digital health platforms can be effective in increasing knowledge on antenatal, family planning and childbirth services in underserved areas (Smith et al., 2023). Adequate knowledge of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services can adequately reduce maternal mortality and enhance a healthy society.

Methodology

Thematic analysis was utilized to identify knowledge of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A content analysis was used to know the knowledge of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth for women of childbearing age at Zaria town. This is to ascertain the effectiveness of similar methodologies in exploring knowledge of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth care.

Pre-birth care

Pre-birth care is the care given before, during and after pregnancy. Mothers demonstrated significant knowledge gaps regarding the importance of ANC, with many unaware of the recommended frequency of visits to health facilities. There are misconceptions and various cultural beliefs and practices that influence the knowledge on this services hence the role of ANC in preventing complications during pregnancy is essential.

Conception Planning

Family planning are practices and methods made by spouse or individuals in controlling the number of children they can have, the timing and spacing between pregnancies, in Zaria, there are cultural and religious barriers that hinders women from adequately using the services. The

religious view of a women having the ability to multiple and love for children by the male counterparts have demonstrated a setback in the use of family planning methods adequately, in Zaria town most men see family planning as women dominated and not a joint efforts of both partners. In this study women indicated a general alertness of family planning methods however, many have limited access to services. Cultural beliefs and stigma surrounding FP also affects individuals' willingness to seek help.

Childbirth care

Safe delivery is very essential after every pregnancy cycle. The knowledge of family planning services is essential and crucial for societal growth. Women in this zone have mixed experiences with childbirth services, ranging from positive interactions with healthcare providers to instances of inadequate care, in Zaria most women also prefer home delivery not always taken by a trained birth assistance. Also cultural beliefs influences some as to preference for home delivery. Despite traditional birth attendants are available some are inadequately trained and when complications arise when not properly addressed lead to maternal deaths or child mortality.

Discussion

Pre-birth care (ANC), family planning (FP), and childbirth services are critical components of maternal health, directly influencing health outcomes for mothers and children. Despite global initiatives to improve contact and knowledge of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth, many females still remain unaware of their importance and availability in Zaria. The study revealed though some women were aware of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth, females in rural areas have showed slightly lower knowledge of pre-birth care. This disparity may be attributed to the demanding daily activities of rural women, limiting their exposure to health information. This aligns with findings from recent studies (World Bank, 2021; UNICEF, 2022), which emphasize the need for enhanced health education and outreach programs, particularly in rural areas, to bridge knowledge gaps and improve pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth care utilization. Mothers demonstrated significant knowledge gaps regarding the importance of ANC, with many unaware of the recommended frequency of visits. The pre-birth visit is at 8 visits according to WHO recommendation while some women hardly utilize the services due to some predisposing factors as level of education, income and distance to health facility. Some expressed misconceptions about the role of ANC in preventing complications during pregnancy. Cultural and religiously factors also affects women in Zaria in using antenatal services.

The findings of this study highlight significant awareness of basic maternal health care services such as pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth care for females in Zaria town. However, there are notable disparities in knowledge and utilization, particularly in rural areas, where awareness of some services are limited. This disparity aligns with global trends, where rural and less-educated women often have lower access to comprehensive maternal health services compared to their urban counterparts (World Bank, 2021; UNICEF, 2022).

The high awareness of pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services in urban and semi-urban areas can be attributed to better access to health facilities, education, and information dissemination. However, the lower awareness in rural areas suggests a need for targeted interventions to address barriers such as limited health literacy, cultural norms, and the heavy workload of rural women, which often restricts their access to health information (Smith et al., 2023). The study also revealed that while most women were aware of family planning services, spousal disapproval and a preference for larger families were significant barriers to its utilization. This finding is consistent with recent studies emphasizing the role of male involvement in improving maternal health outcomes (World Health Organization (WHO), 2020).

The findings underscore the necessity for targeted educational interventions to enhance knowledge of antenatal care, family planning and childbirth services. Addressing cultural barriers and misconceptions is essential for improving service uptake in Zaria town. Health communication strategies should focus on community engagement and involve local leaders to foster trust in healthcare services in Zaria. Other studies support our findings, indicating that knowledge and perceptions meaningfully influences healthcare behaviors of mothers (Morris et al., 2019; Yadav et al., 2020). This research contributes to the growing body of literature emphasizing the need for comprehensive pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth health education for females at all levels especially rural dwellers.

Conclusion

The study underscores the importance of education, access to information, and male involvement in improving pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth service utilization. There is need for the community to learn about the needs of women in pregnancy, during and post natal stages in order to be provided with the needed services. While awareness of basic maternal health services is relatively high in urban and semi-urban areas, rural women face significant barriers that limit their knowledge and access to comprehensive care. Bridging these gaps requires a multi-faceted approach that includes targeted wellbeing education, community

involvement by using relevant stakeholders and policy interventions to enable unbiased use to these pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth for all females, regardless of their geographic location or socioeconomic status.

Recommendations

1. **Improved Health care Education Programs:** A need to implement community-based health education initiatives to raise awareness about inclusive pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth services.
2. **Male Participation:** it is pertinent to involve men in pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth programs through sensitization campaigns to address cultural barriers and promote spousal support for family planning and maternal health care.
3. **Digital Health Involvements:** the use of leverage digital podiums, such as mobile health apps and SMS-based health messages, to disseminate information and bridge knowledge gaps in rural area is necessary.
4. **Policy Support:** A call to advocate for policies that prioritize pre-birth, conception planning and childbirth education and address socioeconomic disparities in access to care.

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